

**MULTINATIONAL OPERATIONS OF MOTORCYCLE SERVICE
BUSINESS IN NEPAL AND THE PHILIPPINES**

A Special Problem in Business

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**CERTIFICATION OF THE ORAL PRESENTATION FOR MBA
SPECIAL PROBLEM IN BUSINESS**

This Special Problem in business entitled **“MULTINATIONAL OPERATIONS OF MOTORCYCLE SERVICE BUSINESS IN NEPAL AND THE PHILIPPINES”**, prepared and submitted by **SANDESH GIRI** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree in **MASTER’S IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION** has been examined and is found to be acceptable in content and form by the undersigned and is recommended for defense.

DR. AMALIA G.DELA CRUZ

Adviser

RESEARCH ABSTRACT

- 1) Title:** **Multinational Operations of Motorcycle Service Business in Nepal and the Philippines**
- 2) Degree:** Master's in Business Administration
- 3) Researcher:** Sandesh Giri
- 4) Name of Advisor:** Dr. Amalia G.Dela Cruz
- 5) Year Graduated:** 2018
- 6) Name of University:** University of Luzon
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8) Background of the Study

The KTM Service Centers in Nepal and Philippines are dedicated towards after-sales service of KTM brand motorcycles and are relatively new in terms of establishment. The service centers in both countries have modern facilities and reflect the trend of modern systems management in the field of automobile servicing.

There has been relatively little analysis of KTM Motorcycle Service Operations and supervision across multiple countries, and the undertaken study provides a unique opportunity to formulate a comparison. The

research study describes key features of the international KTM Service Center Operations wherein the highlight was the on cross-country similarities and differences in the structure of services operations and supervision.

The main purpose of this study is to compare the KTM Motorcycle Service Centre's operations especially along the organization, service process and revenue aspects in Nepal and Philippines. Besides analyzing the operational procedures for providing the basic services and the differences between them, this study also delineates problems facing the institution in both countries. Furthermore, this will give the researcher the opportunity to know the processes involved in the private service sector industries and how various steps are taken to ensure that multi-national corporations can be managed in the face of unforeseen issues.

9) Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to present the cross-national analysis of the operation of the motorcycle service in Nepal and the Philippines in order to provide baseline reference for after-sales concerns of the KTM Service center in both countries.

Furthermore, the study attempted to compare the practices involved in the services provided to the customers by the said entity in Jawalakhel, Nepal and Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines for purposes of

identification and implementation of best practices.

Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the operational status of KTM Service Center as a multinational motorcycle after-sales servicing business in Nepal and the Philippines along the following areas:
 - a. Organization;
 - b. Service Process; and
 - c. Revenue
- 1.1. How do the after-sales servicing businesses in Nepal and the Philippines compare?
2. What problems are identified with the operation of multi-national after-sales service business in Nepal and the Philippines?
3. What measures can be developed to serve as basis for standardization of the global operation of KTM?

10) Research Method Used

The research is descriptive in nature and utilized the sequential type of Mixed Method Research (MMR). The comparative research was carried out by investigating the availability of basic services and facilities provided by the KTM Service Centers in Nepal and the Philippines.

Comparative research is the act of comparing two or more things

with a view to discovering something about one or all the things being compared. This technique often utilizes multiple disciplines in one study.

Furthermore, inferences have been drawn from the findings of the research. The interview questionnaire was customized according to the nature of the interview and based upon such notion, the research is a qualitative analytical research.

Mixed methods research is a methodology for conducting research that involves collecting, analyzing and integrating quantitative (e.g., experiments, surveys) and qualitative (e.g., focus groups, interviews) research. This approach to research is used when this integration provides a better understanding of the research problem than either of each alone. By mixing both quantitative and qualitative research and data, the researcher gains in breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration, while offsetting the weaknesses inherent to using each approach by itself. One of the most advantageous characteristics of conducting mixed methods research is the possibility of triangulation, i.e., the use of several means (methods, data sources and researchers) to examine the same phenomenon. Triangulation allows one to identify aspects of a phenomenon more accurately by approaching it from different vantage points using different methods and techniques. Successful triangulation requires careful analysis of the type of information provided by each method, including its strengths and weaknesses.

(http://resourcecentre.foodrisc.org/mixed-methods-research_185.html, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

In sequential type MMR method, collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data are utilized and the results are used to assist in explaining and interpreting the findings of the study. The sequence can either be utilizing qualitative to interpret quantitative data or vice versa.

11) Significant Findings

Based on the gathered data, the following findings were made:

Organization

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal, has sufficient number of employees to look after the various operations but most of them are new and lack skill. This has partially affected the service operations but with time and skill development, improvements are being seen gradually. Also, some employees lack motivation towards the job which is mainly due to lack of opportunities for development. But the skilled manpower who are present at the Service Center are working hard and giving their best efforts, according to the manager. Additionally, as per the manager's account, the new helpers and even the technicians need to properly go through the SOP (Standard Operating Procedures) and the basic technical manuals so that they can perform at par with the improvements and can function

efficiently.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio City in the Philippines each have a new facility and is relatively new in the two-wheeler market in the said cities, so the business is still adjusting. Management aspects such as job division would help the business as it grows. Constant learning and developmental opportunities should be provided alongside the KTM Service training that is provided.

In terms of productivity ratio, KTM in both the countries is performing well. The management of productivity above the generally stated baseline suggests that KTM management pays special attention while formulating management plan globally.

Service Process

The KTM Service Center in Jawalakhel, Nepal, can be easily located as it is situated in the town center. The layout is well designed and has properly utilized the area allocated. The drawbacks seem to be the parking area which at present serves both as parking space for the vehicles coming to the service center and as the arrangement space for delivery ready vehicles. The insufficient space creates problems specially during peak hours. Allocation of parking and delivery ready vehicle distribution space need special attention, if the service center wants to expand its service volume. Another problem that has been a highlighted issue at present is

the lack of service ramps which is directly affecting the service time and hence the service volume as well. The facility has enough space wherein four (4) extra ramps can be added and this needs to be a priority if the service volume is to be increased.

Additionally, according to Mr. Umesh Dahal, the service volume management is the key target of the service center as everything is dependent on managing the flow of vehicles in the service center. The service volume has been on a rise compared to the previous year but still has not reached the peak. But the issue is under execution phase through the expansion of employee pool and possible dual working shift implementation.

KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio in the Philippines are located in popular and accessible areas in respective cities. The layout plan of Dagupan City is well designed and has incorporated all the important aspects of a layout design such as safety plans and space management. The drawbacks seem to be in the service type distinction and generalized the labor charge schedule. But as the operations are settling, the business is slowly evolving and might look into more options in the future. But at present, operations are still under planning phase and it might not seem necessary to bring these changes right away.

The KTM Service Jawalakhel in Nepal has a significantly high Repair Order per technician which is 186.5, while in KTM Dagupan and Baguio

it is 12.75. Lower number signify stress-free work environment but also signify that opportunities for growth and business expansion is restricted.

Revenue

After special request made by Mr. Umesh Dahal to the financial department, only the revenue of the service charge, spare parts sales and lubricants sale were available. Though the financial aspects illustrated by the revenue seem positive, the lack of extended financial reports means that a clear financial stance was not assessed. Furthermore, on a side note, according to the manager, the facility maintenance cost is increasing and the plan for installing new service ramps might add financial pressure to the overall management.

In the case of KTM Dagupan and Baguio, since they are still in their early days of operation, making a detailed assessment was not possible. But as the operation grows, it will become easier to identify further areas of improvement. But on current evaluation, the area that is affecting the revenue generation is the lack of availability of spare parts. As spares parts is the core earning area of any vehicle service business, lack of parts directly affects the overall revenue.

KTM Service Jawalakhel in Nepal, is better in terms of productivity per employee and per day. Higher productivity suggests increased revenue and prosperous business. KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines are in

their early years of operation so both have lower productivity. But constant market assessment and strategies formulation is necessary to magnify the growth and improve revenue.

12) Conclusion

Based on the findings laid down in this study, subsequent conclusions were drawn. Foremost, it can be concluded that there are a lot of similarities between the service departments in both countries. Most of the policies and work ethics of KTM can be seen being implemented on a similar range regardless of variations in culture, market situation and operational protocols. One key conclusion that can be drawn is that KTM has maintained a global standard even when there is a contrasting market situation. This has made the brand successful globally and shows the automobile brands are adapting localization strategy to better adapt in the new markets.

Another deduction from the study is that there are areas which have not been utilized to their potential. Special focus must be given to facility management, employee training and function division. Additionally, continuous learning opportunities should be provided to maintain efficiency and improve the operations.

Additionally, it can also be inferred from the study that after-sales market gain in a new location is a gradual process which requires patience

and dedication. The level of acceptance and understanding of the consumer market affects the perception of the quality of service and thus it is highly essential to train the employees and provide them with enough exposure to handle clients effectively.

Overall, the multinational operations of KTM is focused on standardization but with close regard to the existing market variables. KTM Nepal has an established market which has helped produce better productivity results but needs to implement modern systems for achieving higher standards. KTM Philippines on the other hand is new to the market situation and can learn aspects from KTM in other countries to make it successful in the coming years.

The proposed measures will aim to formulate strategies and actions to deal with the issues and concerns on the aspect of organization, service process and revenue as it will eventually help enhance their operations and should provide improvement measures for both the countries.

13) Recommendations

The future of KTM Service operations will depend on how they will adapt to the increasing modern trends in service industry. Most automobile service centers in developed countries have real-time online data systems which helps in pre-assessment of and prediction of customer flow over a particular period. This especially helps to manage the volume

of vehicles and hence achieve higher volume and generate greater revenues. KTM in both countries have modern systems implemented and are close in terms of directives, but they still need to learn and grow from systems which are almost obsolete in most of the developed countries.

In consideration of the foregoing conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

1. The KTM Service Centers in Nepal and the Philippines may consider employee training and work-division reassessment for better productivity and service quality.
2. In order to have an objective basis in strengthening the service center operations of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, parallel and further studies are encouraged.

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DEDICATION

**I gratefully dedicate this to my family for always
supporting me and believing in my Dreams and Ambitions**

&

**To the one who has always held me up and helped me
through when the path ahead seemed perplexing.**

- Sandesh Giri

University of Luzon

Dagupan City

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Finally, the researcher hopes that this study will be of special interest to the students learning the practical and theoretical applications related to the program and for those who are on look for such real-life situations beyond their classroom studies.

Thank you.

Sandesh Giri

CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Rationale

The rise in global population and its direct impact on the traffic congestion has helped boost the two-wheeler vehicle segment drastically. The rise has thus helped realize the importance of after-sales business and the profitability associated with it. Two-wheeler after sales has seen a shift in the global scenario with the improvement in technology and the accessibility to information which has made the consumer market more aware. Special attention has been focused on the service department as it pushes for long-term client retention and brand recognition.

A rise in standards of living across developing economies, such as China, India and Indonesia, is expected to influence the growth in adoption of motorcycles in these regions. In addition, superior fuel efficiency offered by motorcycles as compared to automobiles, coupled with rapidly growing population will result to a higher demand for motorcycles in the near future. Developed countries are likely to witness higher sales, especially of medium and heavy motorcycles, with economic conditions becoming more favorable and consumers resuming the purchase of expensive recreational items. (<https://www.openpr.com/news/978102/Global-Motorcycle-Market-Share-Growth-Region-Wise-Analysis-of-Top-Players-Application-and-Forecasts-2022.html>, Retrieved 2018, March 10)

The boom in the two-wheeler vehicle segment can be seen in various

countries in the world. In 2017, India became the largest market for two-wheelers. A total of 17.7 million two-wheelers were sold in India in 2016, which is over 48,000 units every day.

One of the more popular two-wheeler manufacturers in the world today is the Austrian brand, KTM (Kronreif & Trunkenpolz Mattighofen). It was founded in 1953, is Europe's no.1 motorcycle manufacturer specializing in on and off-road motorcycles and ATVs. It is an Austrian motorcycle and sports car manufacturer owned by KTM Industries AG and Indian manufacturer Bajaj Auto. In Nov. 2007, Bajaj Auto acquired 14.5% stake in KTM Power Sports AG (holding company of KTM Sport motorcycles AG). The two companies have signed a cooperation deal, by which KTM will provide the know-how for joint development of the water-cooled four- stroke 125 and 250 cc engines, and Bajaj will take over the distribution of KTM products in India and some other Southeast Asian nations. As on 31 March 2016, Bajaj Auto held 48.36% stake in the company. Additionally, KTM AG has branch in more than 71 countries.

In 2012, KTM changed the way Indians looked at street motorcycles with the then completely different styling of the KTM 200 Duke. The 390 Duke followed and made a mark in the Indian market as a cult performance bike, not seen in the Indian two-wheeler space since the 1980s and 1990s. (<https://auto.ndtv.com/news/why-india-is-important-for-ktm-1664158>, 2018, May 13)

The key synergy of KTM's technology edge and low-cost production advantage of Bajaj Auto is now driving the earnings growth of KTM, this is helping the company to gradually claw back its market share. KTM at the end of 2014 held a market share of 8.7% in Europe and 4.8% in the US. KTM's sales volume have been growing at an annual rate of 25% over the last three years as it successfully made inroads in the emerging market (particularly in China & Malaysia).

The sales volume was also boosted by its ability to continuously launch and supply new bikes which are manufactured in India. Bajaj Auto has exported 53,000 KTM bikes in FY15 as against 24,000 units in FY14, a whopping growth of 121% India has emerged as a key destination for exporting 125cc, 200cc and 390cc bikes for KTM. The bikes manufactured in India by Bajaj Auto are now exported to about 80 countries. (<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/auto/news/bajaj-ktm-collaboration-leads-to-higher-volume-growth/articleshow/48138739.cms>, 2018, May 13)

With 239,000 motorcycles in the business year 2017, KTM extended its leading position as the biggest European motorcycle manufacturer. The sales volume increased by more than 17 % compared to the previous year. Thereby KTM achieved the 7th record year in a row.

KTM has had very good business for many years in the Netherlands. From its inception in 2007, KTM has managed good sales figures. In the first year, it accumulated total sales figure of 609 motorcycles. As of 2016,

there were approximately 970 KTMs sold, roughly 100 more than in the previous year and the highest sales volume within the reflected time period. The year with the least sales volume was in 2010, when the motorcycle sales of KTM reached a volume of approximately 485. (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/806866/sales-volume-of-ktm-motorcycles-in-the-netherlands/>, 2018, May 14)

Looking into the status of KTM in Italy, the number of KTM motorcycles registered from 2013 to 2016 has seen a constant rise in registration and sales. As of 2013, around 4.7 thousand KTM motorcycles were newly registered in Italy, whereas their number added up to around 3.4 thousand units as of 2016. Although there was a slight dip in figures but KTM has still maintained a steady market sales figure over the last few years. (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/804388/number-of-ktm-motorcycles-registered-in-italy/>, 2018, May 14)

During 2017, KTM were sixth overall in the Australian Motorcycle Sales Figures with the Austrian brand recording a 6.2 per cent improvement in road bike sales but a 17 per cent decline in off-road sales brought their overall figures back to 7590, a 12.5 per cent drop on 2016. (<http://www.mcnews.com.au/motorcycle-sales-figures-2017-australia/>, 2018, May 14)

Indonesia is holding steadily as the third-largest two-wheeler market with annual sales estimated at 6 million units in 2016. The prospect of a healthy market helped persuade KTM India into entering the Indonesian

motorcycle market and in the first year, it saw a significant rise in figures. KTM sells the Duke 200, Duke 250, RC 200, RC 250 as well as the Duke 390 in Indonesia. From January 2017 to October 2017, KTM sold an overall 1944 units with KTM 250 Duke achieving the highest sales volume amongst the brand model with a figure of 609 units. (<https://bikeadvice.in/ktm-sales-india-indonesia/>, 2018, May 14)

The two-wheeler vehicle segment has found a drastic rise in recent days and with the increase in technological and aesthetic advancement and the accessibility of high end featured vehicle at a lower price range, it has become the primary transport medium for many of the natives in Kathmandu. The demand for a cost effective and yet brand symbolic two-wheeled vehicle is on the rise and fulfilling that particular need in the market is KTM motorbikes.

The KTM motorbikes that are available in Nepal are manufactured in India. The distribution rights are owned by Hansraj Hulaschand & Co, Pvt Ltd., which is under the flagship of Golchha Organization, one of the leading corporate entities of Nepal. KTM entered the Nepalese automobile market in 2012 and offered only one motorbike product. It later expanded its product range and is currently offering 5 different motorbikes.

With the increase in sales, the need for expansion in motorbike service sector became more important. KTM Nepal, first set-up a Service Centre in Gairidhara, Kathmandu which provided simple to major repairs as per the requirement. The Service Centre center has three service bays

which can handle three vehicle services at once. But as KTM motorbikes took a leap in the market, the service sector started suffering due to space unavailability and concerns from the customers due to long queues. Thus, supply according to demand was not being sustained and although sales were increasing at a high rate, the low volume service schedule threatened the expanding business. So, in order to relieve the pressure from the only KTM Service Centre in Gairidhara, Kathmandu, another service center was set-up in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, which is located at a distance of about 8 kilometers from the first service center.

KTM Asia Motorcycle Manufacturing Inc (KTM AMMI), a partnership between Ayala Corp. and Austrian company KTM AG (Aktiengesellschaft), formally inaugurated its assembly plant in Laguna Technopark in Binan, Laguna on June 6, 2017. The gleaming facility is located inside Integrated Micro-Electronics Inc (IMI), another Ayala Corp. subsidiary. The KTM joint venture is part of the Ayala Automotive group, with production subcontracted to IMI. (<http://motioncars.inquirer.net/50007/ktm-philippines-inaugurates-laguna-assembly-plant#ixzz5DqtpjSeK>, 2018, April 25)

ECG Zoom Zone came about because of the opportunity to deal KTM by way of introduction from Bank of the Philippine Islands (BPI) to Adventure Cycle Philippines (ACPI). ACPI is the KTM Distributor in Philippines. Since ECG Zoom Zone sister companies are well established in Region 1 in terms of Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) distribution,

they pushed to secure the dealerships in Dagupan in Pangasinan, Baguio, and San Fernando in La Union since they are part of their existing area.

The operations of KTM Nepal are linear with the directives set by KTM India. Evaluating the operations in KTM Nepal also helps study the foundations set by KTM India in its operating region. Furthermore, KTM Nepal has an established presence in the national two-wheeler market and thus provided a good opportunity for assessment.

The operations of KTM Philippines have been set-up under the direction and core-concepts as stated by KTM AG. It is one of the newer KTM Markets in Asia and thus provided an opportunity to closely associate and assess its growth from introduction to maturity.

Since both countries are associated with KTM but have operational directives set separately by KTM India and KTM AG, it provided a unique opportunity to compare both the operations. Furthermore, comparing Nepal and the Philippines provided the opportunity to study how emerging markets can learn from established sectors.

Hence, the KTM Service Centers in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal and Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines are the perfect subjects for this comparative study as it gives a unique opportunity to assess the vehicle service industry in the respective nations and get an insight on how service operations are managed. Additionally, since KTM is a multi-national brand, conducting a comparative study on its service departments could help address similar issues in its other global locations and could help in

improving the overall global service volume, service quality and help establish a uniform operation procedure.

There has been relatively little analysis of KTM Motorcycle Service Operations and supervision across multiple countries, and the undertaken study provides a unique opportunity to formulate a comparison. The research study describes key features of the international KTM Service Center Operations wherein the highlight is the on cross-country similarities and differences in the structure of services operations and supervision. This refers to the extent to what sort of organization, service process and revenue aspects have been established under the same brand.

The main purpose of this study is to compare the KTM Motorcycle Service Centre's operations especially in the Organization, Service Process and Revenue aspects in Nepal and Philippines. Besides analyzing the operational procedures for providing the basic services and the differences between them, this study will also delineate problems facing the institution in both countries. Furthermore, this will give the researcher the opportunity to know the processes involved in the private service sector industries and how various steps are taken to ensure that multi-national corporations can be managed in the face of unforeseen issues.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is the foundational theory that is used to provide a perspective upon which the study is based, visual in nature and

allow those reading the framework to understand further the flow of the research study.

The operation of KTM service centers may be explained by the Maintenance Service Concept Model which defines the main benefits that the service company provides to the customer as a bundle of goods and services. According to Bettencourt (2010), Service Concept is a description of the service and how it satisfies customer needs. It should specify what the service provides to customers to satisfy their needs and how the service delivery system is designed to provide customer and company value.

Utilizing the Service Concept Model, this study zeroes in on the comparisons of operations of motorcycle service center in Nepal and Philippines and particularly assesses the various aspects of the operations and how they are being implemented in various regions. The study emphasizes the opportunities that can be derived from the cross-country learnings and can help visualize how KTM is working globally. Aspects such as organizational processes, service processes and revenue have been assessed and compared to find areas wherein improvement is required. Organizational aspects described the norms followed in terms of company structure. The service processes helped showcase the key factors necessary for a successful after-sales operation and the revenue aspects portrayed the economic well-being of the entire operation.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm of Study

Comparison between the various aspects have also helped deduce the best practices which can be utilized by KTM in order to penetrate new markets and grow competitively. The researcher has based his assessment from the information provided by the related departments in both

countries and using the KTM guideless to assess the extent of the operational executions.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed at analyzing the cross-national operation of motorcycle service businesses in Nepal and the Philippines in order to provide baseline reference for after-sales concerns of the KTM Service center in both countries.

Furthermore, the study attempted to compare the practices involved in the services provided to the customers by the said entity in Jawalakhel, Nepal and Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines for purposes of identification and implementation of best practices.

Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the operational status of KTM Service Center as a multinational motorcycle after-sales servicing business in Nepal and the Philippines along the following areas:
 - a. Organization;
 - b. Service Process; and
 - c. Revenue
- 1.1. How do the after-sales servicing businesses in Nepal and the Philippines compare?
2. What problems are identified with the operation of multi-national

after-sales servicing business in Nepal and the Philippines?

3. What measures can be developed to serve as basis for standardization of the global operation of KTM?

Assumptions

The following assumptions were laid down for the study:

1. The interview guide used in the course of the interview with the manager and operations officer involved in the after-sales business is valid and reliable.
2. The inputs given by the focal persons, Mr. Umesh Dahal and Mr. Dan Wigforss, are objective and authentic and, thus, are apt bases for analyzing the business operations of KTM Service Centers.
3. The findings from the comparison and proposed viable improvement measures will prompt in standardization of the operations of KTM servicing business globally.

Scope and Delimitation

The main purpose of this study is to compare the service center operations between the KTM Service Centers in Jawalakhel, Nepal; and Dagupan City and Baguio City, Philippines. The comparison was along the organizational, service processes and revenue aspects. Through analysis of limitations and differences, problems and possible resolutions have been stated and the basis will also establish possible improvement

measures for better operations.

Quantitative and qualitative comparative methods aided by documentary approach have been used as a basis of assessment. Due to the confidentiality of information, the financial statements could not be acquired so the financial reports have not been discussed in detail in this study. Only some general financials related to overall service revenue, spare parts revenue and lubricants revenue have been included.

The Service Center chosen from Nepal is based in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur. The service centers chosen for the Philippines are based in Dagupan City and Baguio. Since, the operations started in mid-2017 in the stated locations in the Philippines, and the locations are sub-branches of the same dealer, the combined data have been used from these locations and have been illustrated as a single entity. Additionally, La Union has not been included as the operations have not started. Also, KTM Service Center in Gairidhara, Nepal has been excluded because KTM in Jawalakhel is a newer facility and thus it is similar to the facilities in the Philippines in terms of technology and would allow closer growth assessment.

KTM vehicle and merchandise sales have not been included in this study. Service department operations have only been compared and other departmental functions have not been encompassed. The exclusion of the other departments has helped in formulating a linear assessment theme for the study variables. In addition, the study does not include jobs performed by the technicians in form of expertise or diagnosis in other

branches or dealerships.

Significance of the Study

At the completion of this study, the findings would directly or indirectly benefit the following:

The Service operations in the Philippines and Nepal. The service industry individuals as well as those who are studying to engage in such operations may derive fact-based information concerning the status and problems of the vehicle service industry in terms of organization, service process and revenue aspects improvement through manpower management, workflow development and facilities improvement.

KTM Management. This study will help the KTM Management to understand the differences in operations in different countries and will help them learn from the shortcomings in each region and make strategic decisions for a stronger and better global management.

The Government Officials. This study will provide them with the required or sought out data in promoting regulation, issuing licenses as well as granting permits, considering the factors in the areas covered and service provided.

Business Administration Practitioners. This study will help them through the analysis conducted in this study which can be used to understand the business sector and make comparisons on a similar basis.

The Future Researchers. This study would serve as a basis and as a guidance for other researchers who may want to conduct a similar study

in their own country or in a related field of study.

Definitions of Terms

The following terms were defined for clearer understanding on how they were used in the study:

Operational Status of KTM Service Center as a Multinational Motorcycle After-Sales Servicing Business in Nepal and the Philippines. This refers to the KTM After-Sales Service business operations in Nepal and Philippines and specifically between the KTM Service Centers located in Jawalakhel, Nepal and Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines with the focus surrounding the aspects such as the organization, service process and revenue generation.

Organization. This refers to the proponents and form of organization of the project, the organizational structure and personnel involved, job description, including specifications and requirements.

Service Process. In this study, this refers to the elements of the facilities' layout design, activities, process-chart followed, and technologies used that help them in providing better service in terms of vehicle maintenance. It also pertains to the available services offered and how they have been set-up.

Revenue. This pertains to the overall revenues/sales generated through the various forms of vehicle service, spare parts and lubricants sold while performing the vehicle

maintenance. It only focuses on the overall income generated and not on profits or losses.

Problems that can be identified with the operation of multi-national after-sales service business in Nepal and the Philippines. This refers to the problems encountered in the organization, service process and revenue aspects of the KTM Service Centers and consequently what measures can be adopted to help solve the existing problems.

Measures that can be developed to serve as basis for standardization of the global operations of KTM. These are the outputs of this study based on the analysis of the findings on the status and problems of the KTM Service Centers to assure improvements in its service quality and overall operations management.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter deals with some literature that may have direct or indirect significance to the present study. The review of related literature is divided into two parts, the conceptual literature discusses the history of concepts, facts, ideas and experiences that have direct or indirect impact on the case study. The second part focuses on the studies that have been conducted prior to this study. It is important to go through and understand the studies that were written prior to this since the previous studies pointed out the essential layouts and understandings required to successfully conduct this case study.

Conceptual Literature

This part dealt with the definitions and the factors that are affecting the vehicle service and maintenance industries. The excerpts that were included in this segment of the study were gathered from various articles, reports, internet websites and online and offline encyclopedia. To further enlighten the readers about the scope of this study, the terms that have been the core aspect of this study were given emphasis.

Motorcycle After-Sales Service Operations of Multinational Organization

Though Nepal's economy greatly suffered in 2015 due to the

earthquake, the auto sector's growth was exceptional. The two-wheelers registration figure touched the six-figure mark for the first time in 2009-10, jumping 102 percent against 2008-09. During this time, sales were backed by the real estate market boom. However, it dropped 18 percent to 138,907 in 2010-11 and picked up to 145,135 and 175,381 in 2011-12 and 2012-13 respectively. In 2013-14, the registration again dropped to 163,945. Since then, it has been growing at a healthy rate.

Traditionally, Bagmati zone, where the Kathmandu Valley is situated, is the largest market for motor vehicles in Nepal. But now, the number of motorcycles and scooters registered in Lumbini, Narayani and Koshi zones is nearing the figures of Bagmati's registrations. Bagmati zone saw the registration of 64,927 motorcycles and scooters this fiscal year followed by Lumbini with 56,793, Narayani with 48,196 and Koshi with 42,429 two-wheelers. This shows that the after-sales industry has a lot of potential in terms of expansion and profitability.

In the Philippines, the motorcycle sector has potential to expand in terms of manufacturing and after-sales operations due to the affinity of the Filipinos with motorcycle use. From leisure and personal use to business needs, the motorcycle is a viable means of transport in urban and rural areas.

Compared to other Southeast Asian markets, the Philippine market is not yet saturated, providing many investment opportunities. The

growing Filipino middle class sees motorcycles as efficient and cost-effective for both personal and business needs. With easy access to credit, sales potential in the country is promising. Consumers are able to buy motorcycles at reasonable prices, with many investors specializing in semi-knocked down units. Local companies have also established technical licensing agreements with foreign brands to facilitate localization of inputs and technology transfer. (<http://industry.gov.ph/industry/motorcycle/>, 2018, April 25)

Operational Aspects of Multinational after-sales servicing business

After sales service refers to various processes which make sure customers are satisfied with the products and services of the organization. The needs and demands of the customers must be fulfilled for them to spread a positive word of mouth. In the current scenario, positive word of mouth plays an important role in promoting brands and products.

After sales service makes sure products and services meet or surpass the expectations of the customers. It includes various activities to find out whether the customer is happy with the products or not. It is a crucial aspect of sales management and must not be ignored. (<https://www.managementstudyguide.com/after-sales-service.htm>, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

After-Sales Service is also regarded as a vital source of profit, revenue generation and competitive advantage in manufacturing

industries. In manufacturing industry, after sales service is focused towards technical assistance, spare parts distribution and customer care which is aimed for successful and comprehensive after-sales-offer. This strategy is also linked with customer relationship marketing. It means that relationship marketing targets for profitable customers through whom relevant strategies can be evolved in terms of customer relationship, trust building. In this relation, after-sales service facilitates interactions with customers and provides assistance to develop the relationship (Egonsson, Bayarsaikhan, & Ly, 2013).

a. Organization

The organizational aspect of After-Sales Service Center consists of aspects such as manpower, organization chart, labor division and hiring processes.

- **Manpower**

The link between manpower and company projects is simple: Manpower is proportional to productivity. The more people available to work, the faster projects can be completed or the more projects a company can take on. Conversely, a lack of adequate manpower prevents businesses from completing tasks. The lack of productivity translates into a reduction in revenue and profit, which in some cases means the business can't stay operational.

When a company employs enough workers, workers generally do not

need to work a high number of overtime hours. The assigned workload is more appropriate because there are more people to handle tasks. As a result, workers usually are less stressed and more rested and alert. Similarly, when enough workers are on the clock, there are more people to check adherence to safety regulations and policies, and workers can seek assistance for physically challenging work. A good number of manpower thus helps prevent problems such as burnout and injury. Lawsuits and workers' compensation claims may be reduced as a result. (<https://smallbusiness.chron.com/importance-company-manpower-23763.html>, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

- **Organizational Structure**

An organizational chart, often called as organization chart or Org chart, is a diagram which shows the structure of an organization and the relationships and relative ranks of its parts and positions or jobs. It is a pictorial representation of a company's structure which indicates clearly the relations between people within the organization.

The order in which the authority and power in an organization is exercised and delegated is important for executing the related activities and achieving the goals and objectives successfully. So, the organizational chart graphically illustrates the concept known as chain of commands and shows the flow of authority, responsibility and communication.

While an organizational structure defines how the activities, such as, delegating tasks, coordination and supervision are directed towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives, the organizational chart is a visual representation of that organizational structure. Being a graphic representation of an organization's structure and hierarchy, the organizational chart depicts vividly the superior and subordinate relationship while it shows the lines of authority and lines of communication.

The importance of using organizational chart is felt since a business organization needs to provide guidance and clarity on various organizational and human resource issues. It is through the organizational chart which ensures that the responsibilities are being allocated, activities are being performed and management authority has been established in a way as needed.

An organizational chart is of great support to create and define the organizational structure, so that the business objectives may be accomplished accordingly and successfully. It not only helps in dividing the functions of an organization in an appropriate manner, but it also aids greatly in developing the structure of reporting while guiding the employees properly, as the connecting lines on the chart show who is accountable to whom and who oversees what department.

(<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-organizational-chart-its->

uses-business-fareed, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

- **Hiring Process**

Successful hiring is a direct reflection of the validity and professionalism of a business. Employing the right people for your business is the most important part of an organization. It is essential to have a good recruitment process to attract the right kind of employees for your business needs. The recruitment process should be cost effective as well as time effective. Recruiting and training can be expensive and time consuming so when recruiting, make sure that the company is are making the right choices.

A good hiring process can minimize the time involved in the searching, interviewing, hiring and training. It can streamline these processes and make the search for viable candidates much more efficient. It is very important to build a positive image to your customers, peers and competitors. (<http://www.lucaspsg.ca/the-importance-of-a-strong-recruitment-process/>, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

- b. Service Process**

As stated by Raghuwanshi and Goyal (2015) in the International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, a maintenance station is a place where in addition to care of the motor vehicle like mechanical maintenance and minor repairs, petrol is supplied, cars are lubricated, cleaned, washed and other types simpler

maintenances that are required daily are performed. In general, it includes several sections like garage general maintenances, mechanical maintenance, major repair shop, tire shop, paint shop, body shop etc.

Maintenance station facility layout means planning for the location of all machines, utilities, employee workstations, customer maintenance areas, material storage areas, aisles, rest rooms, lunchrooms, drinking fountains, internal walls, offices, and computer rooms, and for the flow patterns of materials and people around, into, and within buildings. Through facility layouts, the physical arrangement of these processes within and around buildings, the space necessary for the operation of these processes, and provided the space required for support functions.

Plant Inventory and its control is an aspect that has received considerable attention in contemporary times. This is attributed to the fact that salvaging the challenges posed by inventory drawbacks lies at the heart of management considerations and decisions in companies. For clarity, Plant Inventory Control focuses on Fixed cost, personal cost, acquiring, storing and managing the inventory in such a manner that it is available as and when due so as to cater for contingencies, maximize profit and to minimize wastage, losses or dismaintenance to the customers. It is worthy of note that lost sales due to dismaintenance are enormous. (Raghuwanshi and Goyal, 2015)

One of the biggest changes in today's automotive industry is the

perception of a "tune-up." Ask 10 vehicle owners their definition of a tune-up and chances are there'll be 10 different answers. The classic "tune-up" was once the heart of the automotive business and contrary to some beliefs; today's modern vehicles still need tune-ups to keep them performing at the most efficient levels.

The tune-up was historically associated with the routine replacement of key ignition system parts like spark plugs and ignition points, along with some basic adjustments to help "tune" the engine. Mounting pressure for increased fuel economy and lower emissions drove the car manufacturers to adopt electronics and to do away with ignition points in the '70s, along with the carburetor in the middle '80s. This eliminated the need for the replacement and adjustment of a growing number of ignition and fuel system parts.

As the pace of technology quickened, the procedures required to perform a traditional tune-up changed dramatically. Highly sophisticated ignition and fuel systems are now the norm, using one or more onboard computers to control critical engine and transmission management functions. Things that were once handled mechanically are now controlled electronically through the widespread use of onboard computer technology.

Because vehicles have changed so much over the years, the Car Care Council has introduced the 21st Century Tune-up. This program is

designed to help re-define and educate motorists as to what a tune-up should consist of on today's modern vehicles.

Vehicle owners ask for tune-ups for a variety of reasons, including improving performance, maintaining reliability, planning a vacation, preparing for winter/summer or because they're giving the car to a friend or family member.

To help ensure good performance, fuel economy and emissions, the Car Care Council also recommends that motorists take the time necessary to become familiar with their vehicle from every aspect. Study the owner's manual to become thoroughly acquainted with the operation of all systems. Pay special attention to the indicator lights and instruments.

(<http://www.blaineautorepair.com/general-maintenance>,2018, March 12)

- **Service Center Practices**

In the United States, automakers rely on franchised dealers for virtually all new-car sales and for providing parts and service to car buyers. The performance of dealerships therefore has a significant impact on the automakers' profitability. A survey of US auto dealerships finds that top performers are more than three times as profitable as average ones and highlights three ways in which top dealerships distinguish themselves. Our study suggests that automakers should investigate ways of collaborating more with dealers to improve their performance, because both parties appear likely to reap substantial benefits from such efforts.

To understand what separates the best dealerships from the rest, we conducted 15 in-depth interviews with high performers and then surveyed more than 700 owners and general managers to assess their operational practices.¹Next, we compared the responses of the dealers with their key financial metrics and evaluated different practices to investigate the correlation with performance. The study showed a strong correlation between certain practices and the financial results of dealers and confirmed our experience that operational and other practices can substantially affect the performance of dealerships.

We expected that certain static factors largely outside the immediate control of dealers would influence their profitability—and indeed we found that the brand they sell, their size, and the demographic characteristics of the markets they serve correlated positively with net profits. However, half of the difference in profitability that we observed between high- and average-performing dealerships was correlated with factors more immediately under their influence. The results suggest that even dealers with few structural advantages (such as a flourishing brand or a large market area) can hope to increase their net profits significantly. Three areas in particular stood out.

- **Better practices, bigger profits**

Internal dealership practices can substantially affect performance. The first is talent management. High employee turnover plagues many car

dealerships, yet our survey's top performers had turnover rates that were 17 percentage points lower than those of dealers in the bottom quartile (54 percent versus 71 percent, respectively). When we looked further we found that top dealerships were more likely to indicate that they used formal, consistent talent-management practices, such as structured recruiting processes with a number of interviews for each candidate. Likewise, top dealerships were more likely to provide formal training to their employees (57 percent versus 40 percent of the poor performers) and to use long-term incentives to retain top talent. By contrast, high-ranking managers at average- and poorly performing dealers focused less attention on recruitment and frequently weren't even directly involved in hiring decisions.

Second, we found that some dealers don't appear to be paying enough attention to practices that could help them increase their customers' loyalty. Although 78 percent of the top dealerships offered car owners tours of service facilities, for instance, only 60 percent of the low performers did. Moreover, 63 percent of top dealerships encouraged repeat service visits from customers by sending them reminders about the results of previous inspections, as opposed to only 42 percent of the poor performers. In our experience, focusing on improvements in the service department to win more repeat customers can help dealerships increase their profitability and reduce both their own and the automakers'

customer acquisition costs.

- **Service with a smile**

The more profitable dealerships focus on practices in the service department that promote customer visits. Third, we found that the amount of time an automaker's field staff spends planning for the future and reviewing the business performance of dealerships is correlated with dealership profitability. Respondents at poor performers indicated that the automakers' field representatives spent only 22 percent of their time reviewing the dealers' performance and offering suggestions for improvement (and 44 percent taking orders for vehicles and allocating new cars to the dealers). By contrast, top performers indicated that the automakers' field reps spent more of their time on coaching and long-term business planning

- **Spending time wisely**

At top-performing dealerships, automakers' field representatives devote more time to coaching, performance reviews, and long-term business planning. Although dealerships could do more to improve their operations, our study suggests a larger role for automakers as well particularly when it comes to understanding the specific situations that dealers face. In fact, nearly two-thirds of those we surveyed complained that their automakers' representatives lacked the required knowledge to improve their operations. Our experience shows that when the field staff

of an automaker knows about the competitive threats its dealers face and has concrete suggestions for addressing them the automaker enjoys greater credibility. Attempts to improve the dealerships' operations will work only if automakers overcome these relationship and credibility issues. For many automakers, better training for the field staff would be an important first step. The rewards can be worthwhile. Fully 58 % of the top-performing dealers we surveyed met or exceeded the new-vehicle sales goals their automakers set; only 36 percent of low-performing dealers did. (<https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/automotive-and-assembly/our-insights/how-to-build-top-performing-auto-dealerships>, 2018, March 12)

- **Layout of Typical Service Center**

As stated by Raghuwanshi and Goyal (2015), the internal layout of a garage should be such as to make it water proof, clean and spacious to provide sufficient space for small workbenches to storage and repair benches. Following considerations should be made in the layout of garage and maintenance stations:

- To provide light to the workbenches, openings the windows should be provided at the proper place.
- To keep the floor cleanable, it should be a smooth concrete floor with a surface-scaling compound.
- The doors are provided as many members as required for easy flow of men and materials.

- To form a neat storage for hanging tools, hooks or screw eyes should be provided on the pegboards.
- To provide a deposit of waste material.

- **Maintenance in Entire Workflow**

According to Raghuwanshi and Goyal (2015), In case of workflow maintenance, the following should be followed: Customer to be attended within 5 minutes after entering the Workshop, Opening the Job card with the help of Job slip and explain very clearly to the customer regarding demanded jobs and the cost estimate before commencing the work, the vehicle will be handed over to the shop floor, After completing all the Jobs, as per the requirement of job card. Only after completion of the works demanded by the customer, the vehicle will be passed through Final Inspection, final rejection analysis done reason to each case & technician wise, accordingly counter measure is taken, the vehicle ready status will be informed over phone or through SMS, and the customer is explained properly about the charges.

- **Modern Vehicle Service Techniques**

Modern practices of automobile vehicle faults diagnosis, repair and maintenance require highly trained mechanics. The job of an auto mechanic has become increasingly specialized in the 21st century. With the rapid advancement in technology, the mechanic's job has evolved from purely mechanical, to include electronic technology. Because vehicles

today possess complex computer and electronic systems, mechanics need to have a broader base of knowledge than in the past. Fully skilled modern automotive repairers must have good reading ability and basic mathematics and computer skills. Restoring automobiles to their original form, state and working condition requires mechanics to follow instructions and diagrams in technical manuals in order to make precise three-dimensional measurements of the position of one body section relative to another as well as diagnose and repair the vehicles. (<https://www.collegegrad.com/careers/insta06>, 2018, March 12)

The Internet is even spreading to mechanics, with certified mechanics providing advice online. Mechanics themselves now regularly use the Internet for information to help them in diagnosing and/or repairing vehicles. Service manuals for vehicles have become significantly less prevalent with computers that are connected to the Internet taking their position. (<https://www/collegegrad.com/careers/insta08>, 2018, March 12)

The conceptual framework literature has helped the researcher understand the various intricacies related to the study. It also helped outline the study module and the areas which require special attention. The need for service volume management and improvement has been based on the conceptual literature as they present the basis of formulation on tracking the various issues.

Furthermore, through the conceptual literature the researcher gained valuable knowledge and insight into the changes needed to improve the overall service center standards not only locally but globally as well, and also helped realize the capabilities of an optimized working environment.

c. Revenue

After sales revenue is becoming progressively significant for two-wheeler dealerships, especially in established markets. For many dealers, effective aftersales organization also offers unexploited potential to increase revenue and profitability.

The aftersales landscape is one which is only truly understood from within. It is a complex environment, one that looks like a simple business of 'pots & pans' from the outside but is deeply entrenched in the key disciplines of sales, marketing, stock control, forecasting, product management, logistics, and pricing. (<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/aftersales-strategies-increased-parts-sales-revenue-andrew-selim>, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

The revenue in after-sales is dependent on factors such as lubricant sales, spare parts sales and labor charge generated.

Lubricant and Spares parts relates to the sale of genuine parts to mechanical and collision repairers (I.e. independent repairers). It's a highly competitive environment, with aftermarket, second hand and parallel

importing players eroding dealer/OEM market share – not to mention counterfeit products (as evidenced by the recent counterfeit Toyota parts seizure in Australia). Sometimes the ‘threat’ is a little closer to home, with dealers competing and sacrificing margin to low single digits to win business. It’s not sustainable.

To succeed, Dealers (and in certain aspects OEMs) need to get their infrastructure, resources, parts availability, pricing and logistics all right. Put simply, repairers want the right part, at the right time at the right price. If there is an issue along the line, they want it dealt with fast and professionally. (<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/aftersales-strategies-increased-parts-sales-revenue-andrew-selim>, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

The Labor charge for a two-wheeler service depends on several factors. It depends on the type of repair needed on the vehicle, the time invested, the condition of the vehicle, the spare part to be replaced and the number of technicians to be invested on the job.

- **Problems in Motorcycle After Sales Servicing Business**

Some of the issues surrounding the after-sales servicing business include the following:

- a. The lack of follow-up

Usually after sales team or personnel involved in do not follow-up with the concerned job regarding the feedback and state of repair on the bike. This tends to affect the customer retention on the long run.

b. Service appointments and scheduling

Schedule service during the off-season is relatively easy but due to lack of technicians and resource, during the peak season, appointments are lengthy. so that your bike is ready to go when spring arrives. Proper scheduling and resource allocation are to blame for these problems which are common in all dealerships.

c. The knowledge gap and lack of training

Not every member of the sales staff has the specs and history of every bike and some even must look stuff up now and again. A serious and organized business emphasizes on employee's education and training. Having a business whose staff is unknowledgeable—or, worse, assured but wrong—can be more frustrating than any deep discounts would offset.

d. High prices and parts availability

Maintaining proper and reasonable pricing is one of the primary issues of most of the dealerships. For most dealers, profit becomes more important than client retention which is a negative practice since it demotivates clients from visiting.

Lack of spare parts availability also pushes clients away to another dealership. (<https://www.motorcyclistonline.com/top-4-complaints-about-motorcycle-dealerships#page-2>, Retrieved, 2019, February 10)

Research Literature

This part of the chapter presents the published theses and feasibility studies which are significant to the research study.

The following research papers are related to this present study because they served as reference points for undertaking the case study and relating the current practices towards finding a solution for tackling the various problems:

Motorcycle After-Sales Service Operations of Multinational Organization

Ambekar (2013) made a study entitled “Service Quality Gap Analysis of Automobile Service Centers”. The study aimed at finding the gap between the expected and perceived service quality. It was also aimed to know the then situation of the automobile service industry. The research focused on data gathered through two independent samples namely the personal vehicle users and commercial vehicle users. The findings from the study suggested that the gap between expected and perceived quality was dependent on factors like reliability, responsiveness and empathy. It also suggested that improvement in technological standards can help decrease the existing gap.

The study by Ambekar has been closely associated to this study as well. The need for technological advancement in vehicle service sector has

been made as one of the premises of study. The need for service volume management has also been indirectly evaluated through the effective implementation of factors such as reliability, responsiveness and empathy.

Wang's (2016) study entitled, "Study on the Chain Operation of Automobile after Sales Service Industry", analyzed the advantages in China in the field of automobile service. It also investigated the then present situation of development in the service sector and the chain operations and the plans of chain business model. It also sought out way to improve the whole automobile service industry. The findings of the study suggested that only with continuous integration process in order to make a better development the constant innovation process in order to make a better living can be achieved in the automobile service sector in China.

Wang's study has been associated in this study by looking into the present situation of the KTM Service center. This study is also intended to find innovative measures for a continuous development in order to make the standard of service better. Since the service sector in China has been a basis for many countries, the findings can be used directly for a more innovative and improved approach in KTM Service Centre. Hence, Wang's findings of mutual penetration necessity in service industry has been closely analyzed for this study.

Operational Aspects of Multinational After-Sales Servicing Business

Khan, Singh, Gupta and Jadoun's (2015) research paper entitled, "A

Study on Perceived Service Quality in Two-Wheeler Industry using SERVQUAL Model” studied the gap between customer expectations and perceptions in two-wheeler automobile industry was evaluated. For this study, the data was collected using convenience sampling technique from 75 customers in the form of questionnaire, 25 each from Hero, Bajaj and Honda two-wheeler automobile industries. The study found that there was significant gap between customer expectation and perception in two-wheeler industry. Furthermore, the study provided service managers and administrators an opportunity to identify the dimensions and attributes in which larger gaps between customers’ expectations and perceptions in a two-wheeler industry is found.

Khan, Singh, Gupta and Jadoun’s study presented one of the essential aspects of this study which is the identification of various dimensions and attributes for decreasing the gap in service and volume management. Though volume association has not been related directly in the study by Khan, Singh, Gupta and Jadoun, its theme relating the necessity to identify the perception and importance of service management has been studied as a blended approach in this research study.

Jadhao and Kedar (2016) in their study, “Service Quality Challenges in an Indian Automobile Service Industries” overviewed the challenges faced by an Indian automobile service sector and found the various gaps which will directly or indirectly affected on service quality and factor which

affected the service. The paper concluded with the gaps that were affecting the current position of four-wheeler service industries and their market share in automobile service industries.

In addition, the study concluded that the key to the automobile service industries will be their skill levels of the manpower and the changing Auto environment requires skills such as: Skilled manpower training, motivation, management and retention, Customer service delivery and management policy, marketing and customer loyalty, spare parts management, skills for servicing special vehicle segments like luxury vehicles and green vehicles.

The study by Jadhao and Kedar which has been based on the Indian Automobile Service sector is of importance to this current study because the Indian Automobile Service Sector has a close relationship with the Automobile After Sales Service Sector in Nepal and the Philippines. The close relations thus would also help achieve similar results and the findings could be studied at a closer level. The findings from Jadhao and Kedar's study relating to the skills required in the current scenario has been used to compare the skills illustrated in the KTM Service Centre. The gaps have also been associated to find the flaws in the current system and whether or not the implemented measures can have a positive effect on the service volume improvement.

Gupta (2015) in her study, “Comparative Study of Online and Offline Shopping: A Case Study of Rourkela in Odisha”, tried to recognize how consumer measure channels for their purchasing. Specifically, it progresses a conceptual model that addresses consumer value perception for using the internet shopping versus the traditional shopping. The objective of this study was to provide an impression of online shopping decision process by comparing the offline and online decision making and identifying the factors that motivate customers to decide whether to do online shopping or go for the offline shopping.

The study by Gupta has been used as a reference for comparative style study which is also the central theme of this analysis. The focus of the analysis was to expect the determining factors influencing what and why consumers purchase online and offline as well, why they switch from one way to another and in case of this present study, the objective revolves around a similar axiom wherein the various data are compared, and results were derived. Additionally, the study by Gupta has been utilized by employing the comparing profiling technique used in her study.

Furthermore, study from Ambekar has been used to identify the problems in service sector. The service gap in terms of quality and execution as mentioned in the study has been used as a basis to identify the present problems in the operations in the after-sales servicing business. The consumer demand as mentioned has been regarded as the

mark for standardization and basis for development and improvement. Corresponding to the problems, the required measures have also been identified as a means of resolving the existing issues in order to maintain a global operational standard. Taking into account the perception of the clients, a similar approach has been used in this study but with regards to understanding the approaches for improvement.

Chapter III

RESEARCH DESIGN

This chapter presents the research design of the study. This includes the method of investigation used in the conduct of the study, data-gathering instruments and data-gathering procedures.

Research Method Used

The research is descriptive in nature and utilize the Sequential Type Mixed Method Research (MMR). The comparative research was carried out by investigating the availability of basic services and facilities provided by the KTM Service Centers in Nepal and the Philippines.

A descriptive thesis examines phenomena, group of people, idea or theory with a particular focus on facts and conditions of the subject. A descriptive thesis should be unbiased. The purpose of a descriptive thesis is to provide an accurate account of a subject at the time of the research. If the subject changes after the research, the thesis remains an image of the subject during the time of the observation. (<https://classroom.synonym.com/descriptive-method-thesis-4265.html>, 2018, March 14)

Comparative research is the act of comparing two or more things with a view to discovering something about one or all the things being compared. This technique often utilizes multiple disciplines in one study.

Furthermore, inferences have been drawn from the findings of the research. The interview questionnaire was customized according to the nature of the interview and based upon such notion, the research is a qualitative analytical research.

Mixed methods research is a methodology for conducting research that involves collecting, analyzing and integrating quantitative (e.g., experiments, surveys) and qualitative (e.g., focus groups, interviews) research. This approach to research is used when this integration provides a better understanding of the research problem than either of each alone. By mixing both quantitative and qualitative research and data, the researcher gains in breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration, while offsetting the weaknesses inherent to using each approach by itself. One of the most advantageous characteristics of conducting mixed methods research is the possibility of triangulation, i.e., the use of several means (methods, data sources and researchers) to examine the same phenomenon. Triangulation allows one to identify aspects of a phenomenon more accurately by approaching it from different vantage points using different methods and techniques. Successful triangulation requires careful analysis of the type of information provided by each method, including its strengths and weaknesses. (http://resourcecentre.foodrisc.org/mixed-methods-research_185.html, Retrieved, 2018, July 20)

In Sequential type MMR method, collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data is utilized and the results are used to assist in explaining and interpreting the findings of the study. The sequence can either be utilizing qualitative to interpret quantitative data or vice versa.

Locale of the Study

Locations in two different countries have been chosen for the study. The first chosen location is the KTM Service Center Jawalakhel which is located in Lalitpur Metropolitan City which is the 3rd largest city in Nepal. It is located in the south-central part of Kathmandu Valley.

From the Philippines, two different locations have been chosen but the data has been combined into one. KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio were the selected locations for study. KTM Dagupan City is located in Arellano St., Pantal District, Dagupan City, Pangasinan. KTM Baguio is located in Amparo Heights, Camp 7, Baguio City, Benguet.

The reasons for choosing these two countries are twofold. First, KTM Service Center in Jawalakhel, Nepal started operations in 2016 and the operations at KTM Dagupan and Baguio started from mid-2017 which means that short range progress and comparisons can be carried out on a similar basis. Secondly, these Service Centers serve the same brand and models of KTM vehicles with similar service methodology which would allow an extensive analysis of the Service Department.

Figure 2: KTM Service Center in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal

Figure 3: KTM Dagupan City, Pangasinan, Philippines

Figure 4: KTM Baguio City, Benguet, Philippines

Additionally, the regions are located in prime cities in the respective countries which means that the consumer market orientation is similar and customer service delivery is relatable as well.

Subject of the Study

KTM (Kronreif & Trunkenpolz Mattighofen), is a European motorcycle manufacturer specializing in on and off-road motorcycles and ATVs. It is an Austrian motorcycle and sports car manufacturer owned by KTM Industries AG and Indian manufacturer Bajaj Auto. It has sales and service operations in more than 71 countries world-wide. KTM started operations in Nepal in 2012 and it officially started operations in the Philippines in 2016.

The study is a comparative analysis and for this purpose two subjects, one each from Nepal and the Philippines, were selected. From Nepal, the subject of the study is Mr. Umesh Dahal, being the Service Center Manager at KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel. He looks after all the operations in the region. He was a part of the HH Bajaj for more than a decade and served there in various positions in the two-wheeler service industry. He was appointed the Service Manager at KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel in 2016 and since then has been working tirelessly to manage the overall operations. Hence, he knows every detail and every issue in the Service Center and has the authority to give information about the organization. Thus, he is the right person to be the subject of the study.

From the Philippines, the subject of study is Mr. Dan Wigforss, who is the COO of ecg Zoom Zone, Inc. which is the authorized KTM Dealer in Baguio, Dagupan City & San Fernando, La Union. He looks after all the operations in these regions and is aware of all the issues and information of the venture. He also has the authority to provide all the essential information about the information, so he is the right person to be the subject of the study.

Additionally, the key informants, Mr. Umesh Dahal and Mr. Dan Wigforss, are supportive, generous and helpful and have a high accord from their co-workers. They are willing to help the researcher in any way that they possibly could.

Instrumentation

The research is interview based and has studied the present operations and its outcomes between KTM Service Centre, Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal and KTM Service Center Dagupan City and Baguio. The researcher has interviewed the Service Center Manager, Mr. Umesh Dahal, of Nepal in order to find about the various service operations, manpower division and problems in the service center. In case of the Philippines, the data for the comparison was provided by the Chief Operations Officer, Mr. Dan Wigforss, of ecg Zoom Zone Inc, which is the authorized KTM motorcycles Dealer in Dagupan City and Baguio.

Being a descriptive research, the primary method used in collecting

the data for the research is interview. Therefore, while creating the questionnaire, the nature and background of the study subject has to be taken into consideration and customized questionnaire set accordingly. The questions are short, simple and without grammatical errors.

The researcher used both formal and informal interview as a method of data collection and the interview offered a chance to explore the topics in depth. Informal interview was utilized to retrieve additional information. Furthermore, the interaction between the researcher and the respondents allowed the opportunity to eradicate any misunderstanding of the questions and the answers provided could be easily corrected.

The interview is composed of two parts. Part I was focused on gathering data related to the company and the service center's profile and their establishments. Part II was concerned with the status of KTM Service Center in terms of (a) Organizational Aspects such as manpower and their duties and responsibilities, (b) Service Process aspects such as the business layout, service volume and service operations, and (c) the revenue aspects such as total revenue generated through spare parts sales and collection of labor charge.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought approval from his Professor, Dr. Amalia G. dela Cruz, to conduct this case study. After receiving permission, the researcher asked permission from the Service Center Manager of KTM

Jawalakhel, Nepal, Mr. Umesh Dahal, and from Mr. Dan Wigforss who is the COO of ecg Zoom Zone Inc, Philippines, to conduct the comparative study between the two KTM service centers. Approval was sought to get on hand information on any relevant data which are regarded classified for outsiders.

The subjects have agreed to participate in the interview because they believed that this research will help the researcher, the service centers and future service center plans, on how to improve the techniques and technologies in order to improve service volume in the branch. They also consider that this research will help the future researchers and the other branches as well as future planned locations of KTM Service Center situated in Nepal and the Philippines. Being open-minded individuals, they are open for suggestions, criticisms and new ideas for improvement, so they accommodated the researcher's queries and provided answers in the way they could.

Since, the locale of study is two different nations, in case of Nepal, the researcher conducted an interview using video conferencing. The video-interview helped collect the initial data regarding organization, service process and revenue aspects of the service center. Further exchanging of questions, answers, clarifications and required data were done via email, social media chat and internet calls.

In the case of the Philippines, the researcher collected the data

through communication via email and in-person meetings. Both medium of correspondence helped collect the initial information on service volume, organizational and technical characteristics of the venture. Additionally, E-mail correspondence helped answer any related query and was also used as a platform for exchanging the required data for the study.

Treatment of Data

The research is Sequential Type MMR methods. Structured interview with respondents under the different sub-sectors were conducted to answer the questions on the questionnaire and to generate the necessary data.

The data that were gathered to answer the specific problems were analyzed, interpreted and presented in a narrative form. The problems were analyzed and interpreted using the information gathered from the interview guide which dealt with the standing of KTM Service Centers on its operations in terms of organization, service process and revenue. Comparisons were based on the data collected and were interpreted accordingly. Suggestions and recommendations were based on the best practices derived from either the locations for which the researcher analyzed all the data gathered to come up with the best possible alternative approach that would help improve the operations in both countries.

Additionally, the researcher utilized quantitative analysis methods related to productivity and workout in order to formulate the basis for

quantitative analysis. The quantitative analysis has been based on parameters such as productivity ratio, Labor Productivity Per Employee, Labor Productivity Per Day and repair order per technician. These Key Performance Indicators (KPI) provides as inside into how a service department is functioned in terms of productive output. It helped in understanding how skilled and well equipped the technicians are. Knowing this KPI value, the business might need to work on shaping a training strategy and increasing qualifications of employees as well as finding out whether there are enough tools for everyone in the workshop.

The KPIs that have been selected have been based on the data provided by the key informants during the interview.

- **Productivity Ratio**

The productivity ratio is calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Productivity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Technicians in the Service Department}}{\text{Total staff}}$$

Where,

Total technicians in the Service Department refers to the technical staff such as mechanics and helpers.

Total staff refers to the staff who do not perform technical functions such as managers, CSR, service advisors, etc.

The baseline productivity used for industrial analysis is 3 (three). Higher productivity refers to better utilization of the technical workforce.

- **Labor Productivity Per Employee**

Labor Productivity Per Employee is calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Labor Productivity Per Employee} = \frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Total number of Employees}}$$

Where,

Total income refers to the overall revenue generated through sales of lubricants, spare parts and through labor charge.

Total number of employees refers to the entire working staff who have been hired directly by the organization.

Higher Labor Productivity Per Employee is regarded as a positive indicator for the organization or business.

- **Labor Productivity Per Day**

Labor Productivity Per Day is calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Labor Productivity Per Day} = \frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Total number of Working Days}}$$

Where,

Total income refers to the overall revenue generated through sales

of lubricants, spare parts and through labor charge.

Total number of working days refers to the paid working days.

Higher Labor Productivity Per Day is regarded as a positive indicator for the organization or business.

- **Repair Order Per Technician**

Repair Order Per Technician is calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Repair Order Per Technician} = \frac{\text{Total Service Volume}}{\text{Total number of Technicians}}$$

Where,

Total service volume refers to the overall vehicle serviced in the service center.

Total number of Technicians refers to the technical staff such as mechanics and helpers.

Higher Repair Order per Technician is regarded as a positive indicator for the organization or business.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter includes the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the manager of KTM Service Centers in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal and Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines pertaining to the variables of interest of study. The presentation is structured to be consistent with the order of the specific problems in Chapter 1.

Operational Status of KTM Service Center

The second official KTM service center in Kathmandu Valley is located in Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal. It started its operations in February 2016.

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel is bigger than the other KTM Service Center situated in Kathmandu and is equipped with modern facilities. It has improved layout which is based on achieving high workflow efficiency. It provides after sales service to KTM brand motorcycles. The vehicle models that the service center primarily accommodates are KTM 200 Duke, KTM 250 Duke, KTM 390 Duke, KTM RC 200 and KTM RC 390. It is also considered as one of the best modern two-wheeler service facilities in Nepal.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio started operations in mid-2017. ecg

Zoom Zone Inc. is the authorized distributors for KTM brand motorcycles in these regions. It has modern layout which is based on achieving high workflow efficiency and it provides after sales service to KTM brand motorcycles. The service center provides after sales service to all the available KTM brand two-wheelers in the Philippines but primarily accommodates KTM 200 Duke, KTM 390 Duke, KTM RC 200 and KTM RC 390 as these brands are manufactured locally in the Philippines.

Organization Aspects

Manpower is defined as the total number of individuals who are employed in a company or available for a project assignment or work. In an organization the manpower needed for a particular work and in the future is estimated and planned through different techniques available. Manpower is considered as one of the most important assets of any organization. (<https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/16198-manpower.html>, Retrieved, 2019, February 10)

Organizational Structure

Organizational structure is the hierarchical arrangement of the various authorities, communications, rights and duties of the employees in an organization. It determines how the roles, power and responsibilities are assigned, controlled and coordinated and how information flows between the different levels of management.

Organizational Structure of KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal

The management at KTM Service Center Jawalakhel is managed by Mr. Umesh Dahal who is the chief decision maker. His role is to ensure that all the operations are carried out in the service center efficiently and that all resources are utilized effectively. He is also responsible for allocating various service jobs to the various technicians so that the work volume is equally divided and properly handled.

Figure 5: Organizational Structure of KTM Service Center

Jawalakhel

Figure 5 shows the organizational structure of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel which indicates various positions and relationship of job functions to each other. At present, the number of employees at the Service Center is twenty-five (25). To breakdown, there is one (1) Service Center Manager; two (2) service advisors; one (1) Spare Parts Supervisor; two (1) spares helpers; one (1) head technician; two (2) senior technicians; one (1) intermediate technician; (2) junior technicians; nine (9) helpers; and four (4) cleaners. Apart from these, there is one (1) Customer Service Representative (CSR). There are also two (2) security guards who are outsourced from a security firm. Additionally, in 2016, the total number of employees was 18 which has increased in 2017. The number of employees were increased due to increase in demand for service. Additional service advisor and helpers were assigned so that the lead time could be decreased.

Duties and Responsibilities

The following are the duties and responsibilities of the various positions which have been included in the organizational structure.

- **Manager**

The manager is the main entity in the organization. The responsibilities are to look after all the operations carried out in the Service Center, to supervise the works of all the employees and to assign them their duties as per the requirement.

- **Service Advisor**

The responsibilities of the service advisor are to communicate with the customers regarding their concern with the vehicle, open the job card listing all the major issues, enlist the type of servicing job to be performed on the vehicle, assign the job card to various technicians and helpers, monitor the job progress, recheck after job completion, inform the customer about the job completion and convey reports and concerns to the manager.

- **Spare Parts Supervisor**

The responsibilities of the head of spares are to regularly check the inventory volume, order new spares as per requirement, provide the necessary spare parts as per the request made by the technicians, provide the required spare parts as per the customer's request, keep record of the sales and convey reports to the branch manager.

- **Head Technician**

The responsibilities of the head technician are to work closely with the manager and the service advisor, to look into important service cases, to assist the technicians in their jobs and to maintain the quality of service by providing guidance.

- **Senior Technician**

Their responsibilities are to work as per the instructions provided

by the manager or the service advisor or the head technician, complete the assigned duty related to the vehicle service and repair and inform the service advisor regarding new issues and completion.

- **Intermediate Technician**

They are responsible for service and repairs of the vehicles assigned to them by either one of these: manager, service advisor or the head technician and also to inform the service advisor about the work progress and completion.

- **Junior Technicians**

They work closely with the senior technicians and the technicians and assist them in major jobs. They are assigned mostly relatively less complicated assignments and they must also inform the service advisor about the work progress and completion.

- **Helpers (Spare Parts and Service)**

Their responsibilities are mostly to assist the spares parts supervisor and technicians in their work by either providing them with the necessary tools or by assisting in simple jobs. They are also responsible inventory order management and they must also inform the service advisor about the work progress and completion.

- **Cleaners**

They are responsible for maintaining the cleanliness in the service

center and are also responsible for the assigned vehicle wash duties. They must also inform the service advisor about the work progress and completion.

Organizational Structure at KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines

The management at KTM Service Dagupan City and Baguio is overseen by Mr. Dan Wigforss who is the Chief Operations Officer. His role is to ensure that all the operations are carried out efficiently and that all resources are utilized effectively. He is responsible for making sure that all departments in the organization perform their tasks as per the desired outcomes.

Figure 6: KTM Dagupan City and Baguio Organizational Structure

Figure 6 shows the organizational structure of KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines which indicates various positions and relationship of job functions to each other. At present, the total number of employees is nineteen (19) broken down as follows: one (1) Chief Operations officer, who is in-charge of entire operation, one (1) service manager and two (4) technicians. In the Sales Department, there are two (2) sales supervisor and nine (9) sales consultant, one (1) Brand and Marketing Manager and one (1) Finance Manager.

Both the branches share some resources which include the Accounts and Finance Department and the Human Resource Department. These functions are managed by GreatBev Inc. (GBI) and Napintas Logistics & Distribution, Inc. (NLDI).

Duties and Responsibilities

The following are the duties and responsibilities of the service department positions which have been included in the organizational structure.

- **Chief Operations Officer (COO)**

The COO's attention is in accomplishing the company's business plans according to its business model. The responsibilities include designing and implementing business operations of KTM in Dagupan City and Baguio, establishing policies that promote company culture and vision, and overseeing operations of the two (2) branches and their

departments.

- **Service Manager**

The Service Manager is responsible for looking after the after-sales service operations. The responsibilities of the service manager are to manage the service department and the mechanics, communicate with the customers regarding their concerns with the vehicle, assign the related vehicle maintenance jobs to various technicians, monitor the job progress, re-evaluate the jobs performed, inform the customer about the job completion, make reports to evaluate the overall department performance and convey reports and concerns to the COO.

- **Technicians**

The responsibilities of the mechanics are to work as per the instructions provided by the service manager, complete the assigned duty related to the vehicle service and repair and inform the service manager regarding new issues and completion.

- **Finance Manager**

The Finance manager is responsible for establishing and maintaining efficient administrative and financial systems and procedures to support the smooth running of the operations in the organization. Their key duties include managing the branch finances to ensure effective use of resources to achieve the business objectives, providing timely and

relevant report, ensuring that all financial records are properly stored and secured and providing technical assistance to financial management.

- **Sales Supervisor**

The sales supervisors are responsible for managing the sales consultants and selling activities in their respective regions. They are responsible for strategic sales plans and sales team performance evaluation and improvement.

- **Sales Consultant**

The sales consultants are responsible for closing sales and maintaining good relationship with the clients. They are responsible for managing the sales target and are required to report to the sales supervisor.

- **Brand and Marketing Manager**

The brand and marketing manager is responsible for the promotion of the products being sold by the organization and conducting activities that help boost the image and achieve potential sales in future.

Hiring and Training Policies

Since the KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal is a privately-owned venture under the Golchha Organization, the Golchha organizations' HR team is responsible in the hiring to fill up in different positions needed by the company. Hiring is dependent on the

qualifications of the applicants. The request for additional manpower is also forwarded to the HR team which assesses the requirement and provides the manpower in the requested position.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio are parts of ecg Zoom Zone Inc. The organizational hiring is managed by GBI HR which is a shared resource. They are responsible for all the human source related tasks in the organization.

In KTM Nepal, basic trainings for the new employees are conducted in the Hansraj Hulaschand (H.H) Bajaj training center in Kathmandu and the implementation is monitored on the job by the service advisors and the head technicians. For advanced trainings, the technicians are sent to various parts of India. They are sent on rotation basis which helps ensure that all employees get equal opportunity to learn and develop their skills.

In KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, the trainings are arranged in three categories: bronze level, silver level and orange level where bronze is the entry level training which teaches basic level skills, silver is the intermediate level which teaches skills related to higher range vehicle diagnosis and repair and orange is the expert level training. For these trainings, the employees are sent to the KTM Service Training Center in Laguna, Philippines. In case of general trainings, they are sent in the various branches as per the requirement by the various experts.

Comparative Analysis of Organizational Aspects

This portion of the study focuses on the comparative assessment of the various organizational aspects between KTM Service Centers in the two countries. Quantitative and qualitative aspects have been compared to measure the effective operation in the respective countries.

a. Quantitative Analysis

From the data obtained from both the Service Departments, a quantitative analysis in terms of productivity ratio has been formulated.

Productivity ratios are important in evaluating the efficiency, effectiveness, health of a person, company, industry, or business. It is a fraction of output over input. Output is the amount produced by a person, machine, business, or industry. (<https://study.com/academy/lesson/productivity-ratio-formula-calculation-analysis.html>, 2018, May 15)

- Productivity Ratio of KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel

As informed by Mr. Umesh Dahal, KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal had a total of 18 employees in 2016. Amongst them, 14 were technicians and four (4) were staff (Manager, Service Advisor, CSR and Spare Parts Head). Thus, the productivity ratio in 2016 is as follows:

$$\text{Productivity Ratio}_{\text{KTM Service Jawalakhel (2016)}} = \frac{14}{4} = 3.5$$

This indicates that for every staff employed, there are more than three (3) technicians available. In general, composite reports suggest that a ratio of 3:1 is the baseline so in 2016, KTM Service Jawalakhel was performing above the baseline in terms of productivity.

In 2017, KTM Service Jawalakhel had 25 total employees. Amongst them 20 members were technicians and five (5) members were categorized as staff. The productivity ratio is as follows:

$$\text{Productivity Ratio}_{\text{KTM Service Jawalakhel (2017)}} = \frac{20}{5} = 4$$

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal improved its productivity ratio in 2017 to 4:1. This suggests improvement in work efficiency and better management of the operations.

- Productivity Ratio of KTM Dagupan and Baguio

KTM Dagupan and Baguio, from August 2017 to April 2018, had a total of five (5) employees in the service department. Four (4) of these members were the technicians and one (1) member was categorized as staff. Although there was no dedicated staff for the service department but for the purpose of the quantitative analysis, the COO has been integrated as a staff. Thus, the productivity ratio is as follows:

$$\text{Productivity Ratio}_{\text{KTM Dagupan and Baguio (2017-2018)}} = \frac{5}{1} = 5$$

This figure suggests that the productivity ratio in the Service Department at KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines is high. It further hints that the workforce has been effectively managed from the inception of the operation.

Hence, in terms of productivity ratio analysis between the two locations, both are performing above the suggested baseline. KTM Dagupan and Baguio have a better productive capacity but KTM Service Jawalakhel have been improving their productivity and are headed on the right path.

b. Qualitative Analysis

The comparison will be over organizational structure, duties and responsibilities and the number of employees. The objective of the comparison is to highlight the similarities and differences in operations that are distinctly different according to management, culture and region and to formulate suggestive measures in order to improve the cross-country operations.

- **Organizational Structure**

The organizational structure of both KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio is centralized. Both have a singular point of control such that decisions and policies are monitored from the top management.

Table 1: Comparison of the Organization Aspects

Parameters	KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal	KTM Service Department Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines
Organizational Structure	Centralized Organizational Structure	Centralized Organizational Structure
Number of Unique Job Positions in the Department	Seven (7) a. Service Centre Manage b. Spare Parts Head c. Service Advisor d. CSR e. Technician f. Helper g. Cleaner	Three (3) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• COO• Service Manager• Technicians
Hiring	Dedicated HR Department	Shared Resource HR Department
Training Policy	On Employee rotation basis and as per requirement when new technology is introduced.	Categorized (three training levels) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bronze• Silver• Orange

In KTM Service Jawalakhel, the Service Center Manager controls all the operations and implements the policies that have been set. The manager executes and maintains the policies as forwarded and instructed by the top management which is the Golchha Organization. In KTM Dagupan City and Baguio the implementation of ideas and process is through the COO. All the policies are set and managed according to the instructions provided.

The organizational structure of the service department in both the countries have similar layout. The structure of KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal is more distributed which shows that the work function is more structured and organized among the employees. KTM Dagupan and Baguio require a more structured work distribution as the department lacks employees with distinctive functions. The lack of distribution means that each employee has been assigned multiple job functions which could create disruptions on the core job executions.

- **Number of Unique Job Positions in the Department**

While comparing the unique job positions in the organization, KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal has seven unique positions while KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines combined have three unique positions. KTM Service Jawalakhel is a larger facility which serves a large volume of vehicles for smoother work-flow, job break-down into several positions is essential. But on the other hand, multiple unique position enables the

employees to perform more flexibly as they have only a few areas to concentrate on, which is an advantage over their KTM counterpart in Dagupan City and Baguio. Lesser job distinction adds more responsibilities to the employees in the service department in KTM Dagupan City and Baguio. The employees hired in the position need to be more versatile as they perform multiple functions. But as the facility is new, lesser job-positions help improve team-work and is also economically beneficial.

- **Hiring**

In case of the recruitment and hiring, KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal's hiring procedures are managed by the dedicated Human Resource Department of Golchha Organization. The Service Center manager sends request to the HR team for need of a new employee into a particular position and the team assesses the requirements and conducts the hiring process. In KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, the Human Resource Department is shared between its sister organizations. GBI HR handles the hiring responsibilities for the venture. The requirement is forwarded by the COO after assessment with the managers and the HR team takes the necessary steps. The HR only handles hiring and recruitment on request and is not a dedicated member of the KTM team.

Although the shared resource HR helps save associated cost of operation, it creates difficulty and confusion on understanding the

company culture and often there is miscommunication with the top management. These issues can be managed if a dedicated long-term partnership is planned. Thus, in this aspect, KTM Service Jawalakhel has an advantage as the HR team is already well-aware of the company culture and can employ personnel who is fit for the position. Although, higher costs need to be dedicated to the department but helps in micro-management and in development of strategies which are in-line with the organizational objective.

- **Training Policies**

While comparing the training policies, it was found that KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal has a generalized training category. Every new employee is sent for basic training. For more advanced training, it sends its employees to its local training center in Kathmandu or to various locations in India on a rotation basis. Selected employees are also sent to India when a new technology is introduced, or a new vehicle launch is expected in near future. The employee positions are usually not affected due to training as in most cases the training priority is on hierarchy basis when a new training is introduced.

In KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, the training is graded into three categories: bronze, silver and orange. Bronze level is basic training, silver is intermediate, and orange is expert. The employees, particularly the technicians are positioned on the basis of the training that they have

undergone. A technician who has silver level training is regarded superior that the one who has bronze level.

Both locations have different sort of advantage over their training polices but the training policy in the Philippines is more beneficial as it assures that everyone gets to undergo the training and every technician gets an equal opportunity to prove his skills. It also keeps them motivated in learning new things. In Nepal, due to dissolved training grades, newer employees do not feel the necessity for advanced training. But on the other hand, as there is no particular emphasis, the technicians who have undergone training convey the training to the other members and this creates an environment of learning and succession.

Service Process

This part of the study presents the data involving services offered by the KTM Service Center Jawalakhel and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio its location, layout, facilities, equipment, service volume and sales, spare parts and lubricant revenues.

Floor Layout Plan: KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal

Figure 7. shows the Floor Layout plan of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal. The layout shows that the service center has ample expansion space and has been tactically designed for optimum service handling. The anterior area consists of the parking space and the job card

area which shows that the customers have an easy access and need not spend much time navigating the location. Mr. Umesh Dahal said that due to the extensive volume increase and growing pressure of customers, KTM established a new service center in Jawalakhel. According to him, after sales service is the main determinant for retention and new customer addition so to maintain the growth and sales of KTM motorcycles, KTM Service Center Jawalakhel started operations from February 2016.

It is one of a kind in Nepal in terms of space and inventory management. It has the capacity to facilitate maintenance tasks on more than seven (7) vehicles simultaneously and has modern tools and equipment to ensure accurate performance of jobs. The important aspects of the layout are as follows:

- **QRC Bay**

QRC (Quick Repair Complains) is the area where the minor repairs take place. The location has been assigned a technician and a helper so that the minor repairs can be assessed quickly. This location is important part of the service center and service volume management as it facilitates the most volume of motorcycles.

- **Manager's Office**

This is where the manager resides and also conducts small meetings with the employees or the customers.

Legend	Description	Legend	Description	Legend	Description	Legend	Description	Legend	Description
A	Parking Area	D	Customer bay.	G	Service-bay	J	Bike Wash Area	M	Employee's Area
B	Guard Room	E	Manager's office	H	Service-bay	K	Toilet/CR	N	Toilet/CR
C	QRC bay	F	Toilet/CR	I	Service-bay	L	Spares Dept.	O	Scrap Room

Figure 7: Floor Layout of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal

- **Service Bay**

The Service bay is the main working location in the facility. All the major jobs and service tasks are performed in this location. The facility consists of six hydraulic platforms which helps to lift the vehicle above the surface. The lifts also help perform the tasks more easily. Each bay also has separate sets of special tools and equipment which are necessary during the service jobs.

- **Bike Wash Area**

This is the area where the washing and cleaning of the vehicles is carried out before and after the service operation. The location has a dedicated high-intensity hydraulic hose which helps remove debris and dirt easily. Cleaners are assigned in this area.

- **Spares Department**

This is the area where the spares parts and its stock are maintained. The department is responsible for distribution of spares parts to the technicians as per the job requirement. This department usually houses one head who takes care of the spares sales tally and two helpers who assist the spares head in distribution and data keeping.

- **Employees Areas**

This location is dedicated to the employees and it has a locker for

each employee. This area also serves as a break room and changing are for the employees.

- **Scrap Room**

This location lies as the posterior part of the facility. Here, all the parts that are collected during the service and maintenance tasks are disposed. The room consists of a large bin. Depending upon the volume and quantity of scarp parts accumulated, the scrap collectors are informed who move these unwanted parts from the facility. These scarp collectors are outsourced.

Floor Layout Plan: KTM Dagupan, Philippines

Figure 8 shows the floor layout plan of KTM Dagupan City. The layout incorporates both the sales and the service departments. It has been designed with regards to safety and ease of vehicle management and flow to and away from the facility. The layout suggests that the available space has been well utilized and fire exits have been designed to be accessible from both the floors.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio started operations in mid-2017. As informed by Mr. Dan Wigforss, the facility in Baguio City is still under construction so the floor layout plans could not be accessed. The location in Dagupan City officially started operations in February 16, 2018. This is the first official KTM Sales and Service location in Pangasinan and has

been designed to provide optimum task performance. The important aspects of the layout have been briefly presented as follows:

- **KTM Showroom**

This area of the facility is dedicated for KTM bikes and merchandise sales. The area consists of bike display area, apparel display area and point of sales area. Here, the sales person helps relay information to the customer regarding the bike.

- **Manager's Office**

This is an area on the ground floor which is dedicated for the manager's use where they can also interact with the customers and the employees.

- **Workshop**

This is the area where all the maintenance jobs on the vehicle are carried out. The workshop also has hydraulic platform which helps lift the vehicle above the surface.

- **Storage**

The inventories, spare parts and other related items are stored.

- **Conference Room**

This room is located on the second floor and has ample space for conducting small meetings and training seminars.

Legend	Description								
A	Main Entrance	B	KTM Showroom	C	Bike Display 1	D	Bike Display 2	E	Apparel Display
F	POS/Coffee Shop	G	Manager's Office	H	Workshop	I	Storage	J	Dirty Work Area
K	Hallway	L	Conference Room	M	Bike Showcase	N	Fire Exit	O	Office Area

Figure 8: Floor Layout Plan of KTM Dagupan, Pangasinan, Philippines

Both the planned floor layouts have been optimized as per the availability of the space. The space in KTM Service Jawalakhel is significantly bigger and is dedicated to service and inventory storage, whereas the space in KTM Dagupan is divided into Showroom and Service area. As the location influences the design of the layout, the floorplan is dependent on the level of usage and optimality.

Since, KTM in Nepal is an established brand, the demand for expansion in service location influenced the overall design which is capable of handling multiple vehicles. But in case of KTM Dagupan and Baguio, since it is a new operation, the volume prediction is dependent on the sales which is the motivating factor for a conservative design.

Furthermore, the layout designs have been analyzed on the basis of the following design parameters:

- **Accessibility**

The Service Center location in Nepal and Philippines, that have been taken as subjects for this study, have been strategically located which makes them highly accessible for any new or old customer.

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal is located at the town center and is also situated near a popular landmark which makes it easy for the customers to locate the facility.

KTM Dagupan is located in one of the popular areas of Dagupan and

also near a popular landmark which makes it easily locatable.

- **Sustainable Design**

Both the locations have low sustainability in terms of design. A sustainable design produces more energy than it consumes, costs less to build and operate than a conventional building, and in which occupants feel energized, healthy, and productive. Both locations only fulfill these criteria moderately. KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal's design construction is not suitable in terms of efficient energy savings as several appliances must be used to cope with the elevated temperatures in the workshop floor. This adds to the electricity consumption. Furthermore, no alternate-energy sources have been installed in the facility.

KTM Dagupan has a similar stand point. The elevated temperatures make it difficult to work without assistance from various appliances. Furthermore, no alternate energy resources have been utilized as well.

The design parameters show that both the design have prioritized accessibility over sustainability. The lack of sustainable approach could be because of the location. Also, factors such as lack of availability alternative medium and concern over long-term efficiency could have influenced the choice towards conventional methods.

Service Operation

The KTM Service Center in Jawalakhel, Nepal provide after sales

service primary KTM brand motorcycles but also accepts after sales service of Kawasaki's Ninja category motorcycles. KTM Dagupan City and Baguio provide after sales service specifically to the KTM brand motorcycles only.

Service Charge

The service charge varies according to the labor time spend for completing the particular job and also on the type of the vehicle.

In KTM Dagupan and Baguio, the service charge is divided into two categories. According to the information provided by Mr. Dan Wigforss, the service price is as follows:

Table 2: Service Charge at KTM Dagupan and Baguio

Labor Type	Charge
Standard	\$ 7.68
Advanced	\$ 19.21

The standard service includes basic jobs such as periodic maintenance and simple repair tasks. The advanced tasks include tasks which take a lengthy period of time to execute and require multiple manpower as well. Additionally, the labor charge varies according to the increase in time span to conduct the task as well.

The labor schedule for KTM service centers across Nepal is same. Mr. Umesh Dahal provided the labor charge for various operations and it is as follows:

**Table 3: Service Charge list for Basic and General Service Jobs at
KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal**

S.No.	Job Description	Charges (in USD)		
		RC 200 & RC 390	250 & 390 DUKE	200 DUKE
	Service			
1	Paid Servicing	\$6.71	\$5.76	\$5.76
2	Washing	\$1.20	\$1.20	\$1.20
	General			
3	General Check-up	\$1.44	\$1.44	\$1.44
4	Engine Oil R & R	\$3.84	\$3.36	\$3.36
5	Drive Chain Adjust, Clean and lubrication	\$5.76	\$1.44	\$1.44
6	Coolant Removal & Refill	\$2.40	\$1.44	\$1.44
7	Air Cleaner Element	\$1.92	\$1.44	\$1.44
8	Spark Plug	\$2.40	\$1.44	\$1.44
9	Oil Strainer	\$0.96	\$1.92	\$1.92
10	Clutch Cable	\$1.44	\$0.96	\$0.96
11	Throttle Cable	\$1.44	\$0.96	\$0.96
12	Front Brake Pad Assembly/Spring Pad	\$0.96	\$0.96	\$0.96
13	Front Brake Disc	\$2.40	\$2.40	\$2.40
14	Rear Brake Pad	\$0.48	\$0.48	\$0.48
15	Rear Brake Disc	\$2.88	\$2.88	\$2.88
16	Friction Plate/Pressure Plate/Belleville Spring	\$2.88	\$2.88	\$2.88
17	Radiator (including coolant)	\$5.76	\$4.80	\$4.80
18	Clutch Lever or Front Brake Lever	\$0.72	\$0.72	\$0.72
19	Drive Chain & Sprocket Complete Kit	\$4.80	\$4.80	\$4.80
20	Side Stand (LH Stay)	\$2.40	\$2.40	\$2.40
21	From RH Stay	\$2.40	\$2.40	\$2.40
22	Rear Stay	\$1.44	\$1.44	\$1.44
23	Front Cast Wheel Assy	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
24	Rear Cast Wheel Assy	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
25	Brake pedal/Gear Shift Pedal	\$0.96	\$0.96	\$0.96
26	Tube Handle Bar or LHS/RHS each	\$1.92	\$2.40	\$2.40
27	Triple Clamp Upper	\$2.88	\$1.92	\$1.92
28	Swing Arm	\$7.67	\$7.67	\$7.67
29	Silencer complete	\$6.71	\$5.76	\$3.84
30	Frame Comp Replacement (No other labor charge applicable)	\$81.53	\$76.74	\$14.39

Table 4: Service Charge list for Suspension, Electrical and Engine Jobs at KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal

S.No.	Job Description	Charges (in USD)		
		RC 200 & RC 390	250 & 390 DUKE	200 DUKE
	Front Fork			
31	Front Fork Oil R & R	\$3.36	\$3.36	\$3.36
32	Fork Complete Replacement	\$7.67	\$7.67	\$7.67
33	Steering Bearing Kit (Cone Kit)/ Triple Clamp lower	\$6.71	\$5.76	\$5.76
34	Leg Assly	\$2.88	\$2.88	\$2.88
35	Inner Tube	\$6.71	\$6.71	\$6.71
36	Fork Oil Seal	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
37	Rear Shock Absorber	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
38	Footrest bracket rear LHS/RHS	\$0.72	\$0.72	\$0.72
	Electrical			
39	Main Wiring Harness	\$28.78	\$28.78	\$28.78
40	Fuel Pump (Electric)/Fuel Filter	\$4.80	\$4.80	\$4.80
41	Cooling Fan (Ventilator Comp)	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
42	Starter Motor Assy	\$3.84	\$3.84	\$3.84
43	Battery	\$1.44	\$1.44	\$1.44
44	Stator Motor	\$3.84	\$3.36	\$3.36
45	Fuel Injection/Throttle Body	\$5.76	\$5.76	\$5.76
46	Speed Sensor	\$2.40	\$2.40	\$2.40
	Engine			
47	Engine Overhauling	\$57.55	\$57.55	\$57.55
48	Crankcase replacement	\$57.55	\$57.55	\$57.55
49	Cylinder Head Cover or Gasket	\$5.76	\$5.76	\$5.76
50	Cylinder Head Assembly (Excluding lathe Charge)	\$28.78	\$28.78	\$28.78
51	Cylinder Head Gasket	\$19.18	\$19.18	\$19.18
52	Cylinder Block Piston	\$38.37	\$38.37	\$38.37
53	Valve (excluding lathe charge)	\$28.78	\$28.78	\$28.78
54	Shim Adjustment	\$7.67	\$7.67	\$7.67
55	Timing Chain	\$11.51	\$11.51	\$11.51

Service Types

- **KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal**

There are various types of service operations and they vary on charges incurred. For every new purchase, three free services are provided and after than paid servicing starts. The basic service types as provided by Mr. Umesh Dahal is as follows:

- **Free Service**

Free service is only valid for new vehicles and is valid for the first three (3) servicing. The service duration depends on either day from the date of purchase or the date of last service or the distance travelled. In free service, only the labor charge is free while the customer still needs to pay for the lubricants and spare parts used.

- **Paid Service**

Paid service period starts after the using the free service coupon. In this, the labor charge is added and is dependent on the vehicle type and the time taken for the type of service. It should be done within 120 days from the last service or 5000 kilometers distance travelled, whichever comes first.

- **Quick Repair Service**

Quick Repair Service refer to the maintenance jobs which take a short time to complete. The distinction between a QRC job and free or paid

service is made through observation of the vehicle and through time estimation for the job completion.

- **Major repair and Other Service Jobs**

Aside from these basic service schedule there are major repair jobs which and other repairs that are performed as well but are dependent on the need for maintenance which could be due to periodic need or due to wear of the part. Major Repair takes comparatively more time.

- **KTM Dagupan City and Baguio**

There are two primary service types: Free Service and paid service. Free Service is valid only on new bikes and on basic maintenance tasks. The paid service is any sort of maintenance job which is liable for labor charge payment.

Any other maintenance job that is qualified for a warranty claim is also free of labor charge. Such cases are dependent on the warranty clause.

Warranty Criteria

Both Mr. Umesh Dahal and Mr. Dan Wigforss had similar notions about the warranty criteria. According to both, it is important to maintain the service schedule in order to avail the two (2) year warranty coverage. The general warranty terms and conditions states that warranty claims are rejected on the following grounds:

- The customer missed even just one of the inspections or maintenance tasks described in the owner's Manual, or had it performed with a delay.
- The inspection, maintenance, and repair work performed on the motorcycle were not performed by a dealer authorized by KTM.
- Maintenance and repair work performed on the motorcycle deviates from the technical requirements, specifications, and regulations stipulated by the manufacturer.
- The maintenance and repair work performed on the motorcycle made use of spare parts that are not approved by KTM.
- The motorcycle has been, in any way whatsoever, converted, modified, or equipped with parts that do not belong to the scope of equipment expressly approved by KTM.
- The motorcycle was stored and transported in a technically unsuitable manner.
- The motorcycle was used contrary to its intended use in motor sports for competitions, races, and attempts at setting new records.

KTM in both the countries follow the above-mentioned criteria for warranty claims but KTM in Nepal has an additional criterion for availing warranty. The criteria states that second-hand purchasers are not qualified for warranty and it is automatically void once there is change in

ownership. But KTM in Philippines offers warranty to second-hand purchasers once the change in ownership has been registered.

Work-Process Flow-Chart

Work-process in the KTM Service Center is dependent on the type of job or the type of servicing required in the vehicle. According to the Mr. Umesh Dahal and Mr. Dan Wigforss, there are various phases involved in the process and every customer must be handled differently so the process execution is slightly flexible. Work-flow process in KTM has been standardized in order to meet the service protocol globally but varies slightly due to availability of equipment and machineries.

Figure 9 shows the work-process flowchart in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal and the brief description of the processes involved are as follows:

- **Identify the type of Vehicle Service Request**

This is the first stage wherein the problem description is noted and on the basis of the problems recognized the service type is allocated.

- **Quick Repair Jobs**

Quick repair complains are those which are associated with minor issues that can be solved in a short time such as gear lever replacement, brake-shoe replacement, etc.

Figure 9: Work Flowchart of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel

- **Opening Job Card**

A job card is a written record of the customer complain and issues that have been narrated. It also consists of the diagnosis made through the observation and initial test by the service advisor. It also acts as an agreement paper between the service center and the customer regarding the consent to perform the listed operations on the vehicle. The job card is of two types: QRC and Major complain Job Card.

- **Job Assignment**

The job is assigned to various technicians according to the complexity and time requirement of the job. Complex cases are mostly handled by the head technician or the senior technicians. These tasks include jobs such as engine overhaul, electrical issues, transmission issues, tec. The less severe issues are handled by the junior technicians.

- **Vehicle Wash**

Vehicle is usually washed before the job is started so that all dirt and debris can be cleared, and work can be carried out in a cleaner way. Often, vehicles are sent for wash after the task is completed. This is done when the task might require working with grease or engine oil. The facility has a dedicated wash bay to perform these tasks.

- **Request for Spares Parts**

Once the job card has been handed to the technicians, the

technicians make a request at the spare parts department for the required parts. The department is also the location for making payments or any purchases. The spare parts are handled out and are listed on the job card according to the identity code of the part.

- **Service bay**

This is the location where all the major jobs are carried out. The service bay has hydraulic platforms, drawers for tools, pneumatic lines for pneumatic wrenches and tools board for organizing the tools.

- **Job Progress Enquiry**

The task of checking the progress is important as it helps to make estimation on the tentative completion time and to calculate if more volume of vehicles can be received by the service center. The job progress also gives an idea on the execution of the task. The observation of the progress ensures proper feedback to the customers as well and can help divide the work pressure too.

- **Inform the Service advisor about job completion**

The technician briefs the service advisor about the work carried out and the service advisor checks the list of jobs to be performed and performs a final check to ensure all jobs have been implemented.

- **Informing the customer and closing the job card**

After finalizing that the service has been performed as per the

requests made, the customer is contacted, and all the list of operations are briefed to the customers. Once an approval of the jobs performed is acknowledged by the customer, the job card is closed.

- **After Service Follow-up**

In order to maintain a close relationship with the customer, follow-up calls and messages are sent to the customer to ask about the state of the vehicle and to assess their level of satisfaction.

Figure 10 shows the work-process flowchart in KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines. The flow-chart is divided along five parameters, namely; reception, job control, technician, parts and quality inspection.

First, the job order is received from the client after scheduling an appointment. Then the bike checklist is performed, and repair order and parts request are confirmed by the client.

After the job order is numbered and sequenced and Once the slot is available, the inspection sheet is given to the technician and the technician is timed-in. The technician then confirms the vehicle's identification number (VIN) and pre-inspection is performed and required parts are requested. The parts specialist provides the required spare parts and the job is completed. If any additional recommended work is required, then the client is informed else the technician is timed-out and the quality check is performed. Once assured, the client is informed.

Figure 10: Work Flowchart of KTM Service Dagupan and Baguio

KTM Service Department in both the countries follow similar norms and have an almost uniform outline for service workflow process. Job card entry method is the primary difference between the two locations wherein KTM Nepal ensures that an agreement in written form is received from the customer while in KTM Philippines, the agreement is solely on verbal basis.

Apart for this, the other areas where the differences exist are the job division and mandatory wash process which are not followed in KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines.

Service Volume

Service Volume pertains to the assessment of the number of vehicles that the service center facilitates. It is also the assessment of the efficiency of the service center in handling the volume of vehicles with regards to the available tools and facilities.

- **Service Volume at KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal**

According to the manager, Mr. Umesh Dahal, the service volume is rising at the service center. He also provided the service volume report of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel from August 2017 to December 2017 in order to show the rise in volume of the vehicles. He did not hesitate to provide the data related to the service volume because he believed that it would be of big help to this study.

Table 5: KTM Service Center Jawalakhel Service Volume Report

	2017				
	Periodic Free Service	Periodic Paid Service	Major Repairs	QRC	Monthly Total
August	118	117	233	334	802
September	113	125	146	301	685
October	131	109	116	317	673
November	135	149	161	360	805
December	133	130	183	319	765
Total	630	630	839	1631	3730

In August 2017, the service center received a volume of 802 vehicles, amongst which QRC jobs were the highest. The exceptional volume was one of the highest recorded vehicle volumes in the year.

The major Nepalese festivals, Dashain and Tihar, are celebrated in the months of September and October during which businesses remain closed and people travel across the country for celebrations with their family. Due to the festival season, the volume slightly dipped in these months. But overall, from August to December 2017, the average recorded volume was 746 which amounted to a total of 3730 vehicles within that duration.

The exceptional volume also helps predict that sales of KTM motorcycles have been on the rise in Nepal which is a positive prospect for the service department in terms of opportunities for expanding the revenue generation.

- **Service Volume at KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines**

For evaluating the service volume, the data from KTM Dagupan and KTM Baguio have been combined.

Mr. Dan Wigforss provided the service volume report of KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio from August 2017 to December 2017. He provided the report on short notice because he believed that it would help this study.

Table 6: KTM Dagupan and Baguio Combined Service Volume Report

	2017				
	Periodic Free Service	Periodic Paid Service	Major Repairs	QRC	Total
August	-	4	2	-	6
September	1	1	0	1	3
October	6	1	0	1	8
November	6	7	2	2	17
December	4	10	0	3	17
Total	17	23	4	7	51

Based on the report, from August 2017 to December 2017, Dagupan and Baguio have received a combined volume of 51 vehicles. Additionally, although there are no actual QRC (Quick Repair Complain) and Major Repair job distinctions but for uniformity in data comparison the tasks have been differentiated into these categories.

From the data it can be observed that the service volume is significantly rising when compared to the operations in the early months. The volume has seen a drastic rise in November and December and which led to a combined volume of 51 vehicles.

The report shows a decent volume even though the facilities in Baguio City are still under construction. This hints that the volume should see a rise in numbers once that facility in Baguio is fully functional.

The volume observed in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal could be used as a benchmark for service performance by KTM Dagupan and Baguio. The management of large volumes in KTM Nepal also provides

a learning opportunity for future workshop designs in KTM Philippines.

Modernization in Information Management

This section focuses on the various modern information management systems used for service information supervision by the service departments in KTM Nepal and KTM Philippines.

- **SAP Software of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal**

SAP (Systems, Applications, and Products) software offers business a platform in the form of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software to manage their separate databases that run their company. The software is used in KTM Service Center Jawalakhel to maintain records of the various service and repair tasks performed and also for inventory, sales and financial management. The jobs that have been written on the physical job cards are also encoded into the database available in the SAP package. The entries help to keep track of the vehicle maintenance history and also helps on cross-referencing information from other service branches. The system was introduced to KTM Service Center Jawalakhel from July 2016 and since has been used regularly.

- **KTM Dealernet of KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines**

KTM Dealernet is an online portal which helps the various KTM dealers store data related to vehicle sales and service, communicate for

transactions, access to updated reports and manage the dealer operations as well. KTM Dagupan and Baguio both actively use the portal for service registration and record keeping.

Both countries have a unique information database system but KTM Dagupan and Baguio use the official portal provided by KTM. The service center in Nepal utilizes SAP since KTM in Nepal and India work under the supervision of Bajaj Auto Limited and SAP is accessible across both the departments. Utilizing dealernet would not allow cross organization information communication as it is only available for KTM dealers and not for Bajaj dealers. As for KTM Dagupan and Baguio, they are solely under the KTM management so using KTM Dealernet is suitable.

Comparative Analysis of Service Process

This portion of the study focuses on the comparison of the service processes between KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio. Quantitative and qualitative measures have been used for comparison.

a. Quantitative Analysis

Repair Order per Technician (ROPT) has been used for quantitative analysis of service process between the service operations in both the countries. The measure has been utilized in this study because it encapsulates how the available labor force has been utilized in achieving

the service volume. Furthermore, it also helps assess the work environment and to understand if the employees are extensively occupied or can work stress-free.

- **ROPT in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel**

The analysis of ROPT in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal is as follows:

In 2017, from August 2017 to December 2017, the total service volume was 3,730 and the total number of technicians in the service center was 20.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Repair Order Per Technician} &= \frac{3730}{20} \\ &= 186.5 \end{aligned}$$

The ROPT in KTM Service Jawalakhel is 186.5 which indicates that the labor force has been kept busy and the working hours have been well utilized.

- **ROPT in KTM Dagupan and Baguio**

The analysis of ROPT in KTM Dagupan and Baguio from August 2017 to December 2017 is as follows:

From August 2017 to December 2017, the combined total service volume was 51 and there were four (4) technicians.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Repair Order Per Technician} &= \frac{51}{4} \\ &= 12.75 \end{aligned}$$

The ROPT in KTM Dagupan and Baguio is 12.75 which indicates that the labor force has been working relatively stress-free.

While comparing the Service Departments in Nepal and Philippines, the technicians in Nepal have a busier schedule and need to be more diligent. On the other hand, the working environment in the Philippines is stress-free. But looking through another perspective, the branches in Philippines are not getting enough vehicle volume which indicates that the market situation is either new or the market approach is not effective. This has in turn lead to the low ROPT.

Although the low volume environment allows the employees to work stress-free, it also signifies that opportunities for learning and growth is limited.

On the other hand, even though the technicians in Nepal face stressed work environment, they maintain a healthy vehicle volume which is a positive indication for increase in revenue generation and provides opportunities to learn and grow faster.

a. Qualitative Analysis

The comparison will be over the floor layout plan, service charge, service types, warranty criteria, work-process flowchart and enterprise software used.

Service Volume					
2017 (Aug-Dec)	KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal				
	Periodic Free Service	Periodic Paid Service	Major Repairs	QRC	Total
	630	630	839	1631	3730
	KTM Service Department Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines				
	17	23	4	7	51
Parameters	KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal		KTM Service Department Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines		
Floor Layout Plan	Utilization and Availability				
<i>Efficient Space Utilization</i>	Yes		Yes		
<i>Flexibility in arrangement</i>	Yes		Yes		
<i>Ease of Circulation</i>	Yes		Yes		
<i>Allocation of Safety Measures</i>	Yes		Yes		
<i>Dedicated QRC Bay</i>	Yes		No		
<i>Dedicated Wash Bay</i>	Yes		No		
<i>Multiple Service Ramps</i>	Yes		No		
Service charge	Detailed		Generalized		
Service types	Multiple Category <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free • Paid • Major • QRC 		Multiple Category <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free • Paid 		
Warranty Criteria	As per KTM and HH Bajaj guidelines		As per KTM guidelines		
Work-Process Flowchart	Sequential		Sequential		
Use of Enterprise Software or Web-Portal	SAP Software		KTM Dealernet		

- **Service Volume**

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal has substantially higher service volume than KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio combined. Even though, KTM Service Jawalakhel started its operations in February 2016, in the second year of its operations, from August 2017 to December 2017, the total volume achieved was 3,730. This extensive flow of vehicle signifies that the operations have been managed efficiently and successfully.

In comparison, the service volume at KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio is significantly lower. From the start of operations in August 2017 to December 2017, the combined volume recorded was 51. Although the volume is significantly lower than Nepal, it is on the verge of increment as it has showed a rise in 2018 (based on the data in 2018, Appendix G).

The selected location from the two countries have a significant difference in volume but the lower quantity in the Philippines is also due to the fact the KTM motorcycle's affordable range of vehicles (200 Duke and RC 200) were officially introduced in the country in mid-2016 and they have become accessible in Pangasinan and Benguet regions since mid-2017, which is very recent. The trend is still catching on because the two-wheeler market segment is very competitive in the Philippines. But the service volume is gradually improving and as the operation extends to other regions, the volume will improve.

A reason for higher volume in Nepal is that KTM motorcycles are bought by the consumers as a regular transport medium. Since, the four-wheeler segment endures higher pricing due to aggressive import taxes, consumers find motorcycles as an affordable option. Due to this reason there is a relatively higher quality of two-wheelers in Nepal. And, utilizing this fact, KTM offered motorbikes in the 200 and 390 cc range which is a low-competition segment in Nepal and thus has managed to find success and consequently higher service volume as well. But in case of the Philippines, high-end motorcycles such as KTM are regarded as luxury vehicles and have an emerging market as well. Also, since four-wheelers are comparatively affordable in the Philippines, consumers are more inclined towards purchasing cars rather than luxury bikes so there are only a selective group of enthusiasts in this bike-segment. Being relatively young in the market segment and with an evolving group of consumers, service volume in KTM Dagupan City and Baguio have a lower volume.

- **Floor Layout Plan**

The floor layout plan has been compared with respect to five various parameters. The parameters have been identified after analyzing the layout plan of the two locations and identifying key design points.

- Efficient Space Utilization

Both the locations have efficiently utilized the space that has been

allocated. Front to back allocation has been well organized. The space provided has been divided based on the requirement in carrying out the particular function.

- Flexibility in arrangement

Both the locations have areas which can be interchanged when required. This shows that the facilities have been designed for flexible change when needed.

- Ease of Circulation

Circulation is the route that people follow as they move from one place to another in the facility. Both the locations have ample space dedicated for circulation of people and movement of materials inside the facilities.

- Allocation of Safety Measures

In any layout design, allocation of safety measures is very essential, and both the locations have taken measures to make sure that safety is emphasized. Fire-extinguishers have been well placed and safety exits have been allocated in case of fire break-out or in case of occurrence of any big calamity.

- Dedicated QRC Bay

Though both the facilities have a well-designed layout, only KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal allocates has a dedicated QRC bay for

maintenance that can be performed in a short time and is located at the front area of the facility.

A separate QRC area helps save time for both the technicians and the customers. KTM Dagupan City does not have a dedicated QRC bay as the such job distinction has not been allocated yet.

- Dedicated Wash Bay

KTM Dagupan and Baguio do not have a dedicated wash bay which is available in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel. A dedicated wash bay helps keep the service bay clean and also helps add revenue.

- Multiple Service Ramps

KTM Service Center in Jawalakhel, Nepal has six (6) dedicated service ramps whereas KTM Dagupan and KTM Baguio have one (1) each. In initial operation phase single ramps will serve the job but multiple ramps could help during sudden volume increase.

- **Service Charge**

While comparing the service charge schedule, it was found that KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal has a detailed service schedule. The service charge has been differentiated into several categories which helps allocate the concerned labor charges with clear distinction. On the other hand, the service charge in KTM Dagupan City and Baguio have been generalized into two categories: standard and advanced.

The labor charge is dependent on the time a technician will need to dedicate for solving the problem in the motorcycle.

The detailed distinction in KTM Service Jawalakhel helps the service advisors in accurate and fair labor charge allocation. Generalized labor schedule in KTM Dagupan City and Baguio helps keep the task simple but might create problems while allocating labor for jobs which are specific.

- **Service Types**

KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal has four (4) different service categories: Free, Paid, Major and QRC while KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines have only two: Free and Paid.

The multiple service categories help easily distinct the severity of the job and time allocation, priority and job assignment can be done accordingly. This also helps in volume management as jobs with severe cases can be assigned to the experts so that those maintenance jobs can be completed with good efficiency within less time.

- **Warranty Criteria**

Both the locations follow the guidelines provided by KTM while deciding if a vehicle is qualified for warranty claim.

KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal has an additive clause which mentions that in case of transfer of ownership, the warranty can no longer be claimed, and all repair work will be liable to labor charge.

- **Work-Process Flowchart**

Both KTM in Nepal and Philippines follow the sequential work-process which means that the tasks are accomplished by following the step by step procedure. The sequential process helps maintain uniformity in execution across several branches.

- **Enterprise Software/Portal**

Both the businesses use a form of enterprise software which is a large-scale software that is aimed to support or solve the problems of an entire organization. In KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal SAP software is used while in KTM Dagupan and Baguio, KTM Dealernet is used. KTM Dealernet is an online portal which serves a similar function to that of an enterprise software. It is officially owned by KTM and is distributed only to KTM motorcycle dealers.

Even though KTM Service Jawalakhel is a part of KTM, it does not use KTM Dealernet. This is because KTM and Bajaj Auto Ltd. work under a partnership in India and Nepal, and since it is a joint operation, SAP helps for information sharing and database management between KTM and Bajaj as it's a more flexible choice.

Revenue

The service center's detailed financial could not be assessed because the financials reports are regarded highly confidential. But through special

request, Mr Umesh Dahal and Mr. Dan Wigforss provided the revenue reports of service charge, spare parts sold, and the lubricants sold. Although these financials do not provide a complete financial report, but they help to understand and forecast the monetary targets of service department.

Labor charge refers to the service charge per vehicle job. It is dependents on the type of service and on the vehicle. Service charges are different in both the locations because of market conditions and the span of operation.

Spare parts sales refer to an inventory that is used to replace failed parts that need periodic replacement. As assessed from the information provided by Mr. Umesh Dahal and Mr Dan Wigforss, the price for the parts are different in both countries due to the regional regulations in import and availability of local manufacturing plant.

Lubricant sales refer to the sale of lubricant oil, coolant and other oil related to the vehicle. The price of lubricant oils is also variable in both the countries.

Revenue of KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal

The report provided by Mr. Umesh Dahal was for the fiscal year 2017 and 2018 and the data has been illustrated in table 7.

According to Mr. Umesh Dahal, in the fiscal year 2017-2018, the

total service charge revenue was **\$32,340.90**. Furthermore, the revenue generated through spare parts sales was **\$320,667.31**. Also, in the fiscal year 2017-2018, the total lubricant sales were **\$110,519.17**. Overall, the total revenue for FY 2017-2018, was **\$463,527.38**. This is **44.49 %** increase from the previous year, FY 2016-2017(Appendix E). According to Mr. Umesh Dahal, the significant increase in the overall revenue is due to higher volume of vehicles that the service center facilitated in 2017.

Table 7: KTM Service Center Jawalakhel Service Charge, Spares Parts and Lubricants Sale Revenue

	Fiscal Year 2017-2018
Service Charge	\$ 32,340.90
Spares Sales	\$ 320,667.31
Lubricants Sales	\$ 110,519.17
Total	\$ 463,527.38

a. Revenue of KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines

The report provided by Mr. Dan Wigforss has been illustrated in table 8 as a combined account of the revenues generated by KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio from August 2017 to early December 2017.

Table 8: KTM Dagupan & Baguio Service Charge, Spares Parts and Lubricants Sale Revenue

	2017 (Aug-Dec)	2018 (Jan-Apr)	2017-2018
Service Charge	\$ 86.59	\$ 99.88	\$ 186.48
Spares Sales	\$ 430.10	\$ 543.60	\$ 973.70
Lubricants Sales	\$ 438.69	\$ 669.23	\$ 1,107.91
Total	\$ 955.38	\$ 1,312.72	\$ 2,268.09

Based on the report, the combined service revenue from August 2017 to early April 2018 was **\$ 186.48**. The combined spare parts sales revenue was **\$ 973.70**, and the combined lubricant sales revenue was **\$1,107.91**. The overall revenue was **\$2,268.09**.

The report suggests that revenues are increasing and have improved significantly in the first 3 months of 2018 when compared to the revenue generated in 2017. Since, in the early stages of the operations, making exact assumptions will not be possible but on a general note, the rising figures show a positive phase in terms of revenues.

Comparative Analysis of Revenue Aspects

This portion of the study focuses on the comparison of the revenue aspects between KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio. The comparison will be over the revenue generated through collection of labor charge and sales of spare parts and lubricants.

Analysis of Revenue Aspects

For the analysis of the revenue, the total sales of lubricants, spare parts and labor charge collection for the year 2017-2018 from KTM Service Centers in Nepal and the Philippines were considered. From the comparison it can be stated that the revenues between KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio is significantly different.

	Revenue Generated	
	KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal	KTM Service Department Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines
	FY 2017-2018	2017-2018
Service Charge	\$ 32,340.90	\$ 186.48
Spares Sales	\$ 320,667.31	\$ 973.70
Lubricants Sales	\$ 110,519.17	\$ 1,107.91
Total	\$ 463,527.38	\$ 2,268.09

Revenues in KTM Service Jawalakhel are high due to the high service volume received by the facility as a result of the well-established two-wheeler vehicle segment in Nepal. Revenues generated in Nepal was **\$463,527.38** and in comparison, in KTM Dagupan and Baguio, from August 2017 to April 2018, it was **\$ 2,268.09**.

The reason for a low yield in KTM Dagupan City and Baguio is the relatively new market operations. As the market grows, the business will improve in terms of revenues as well. The improvement in revenues in 2018 is already an optimistic indication for improvement in near future.

Quantitative Analysis of the Revenue Aspects

Labor productivity per employee and labor productivity per day have been used as parameters for quantitative analysis of the revenue aspects. The analysis has been performed using these measures because the ratios have input variables which can be extracted from the data provided for this study. Furthermore, measuring productivity per employee and per day

helps visualize how effectively the manpower and available work schedule have been utilized in order to boost revenue.

Labor productivity per employee (LPPE)

LPPE is defined as the total revenue generated by each employee. Higher labor productivity per employee signifies that the workforce utilized is highly efficient.

○ **Labor Productivity Per Employee at KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel**

The analysis for labor productivity per employee of KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel Nepal is as follows:

In 2016, the total revenue generated was \$ 320,802.28 (Appendix E) and the total number of employees was eighteen (18).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Labor Productivity Per Employee} &= (\$ 320,802.28)/18 \\ &= \$ 17,822.35 \end{aligned}$$

In 2017, the total revenue generated was \$ 463,527.38 and the total number of employees was twenty-five (25).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Labor Productivity Per Employee} &= (\$ 463,527.38)/25 \\ &= \$ 18,541.09 \end{aligned}$$

The labor productivity per employee improved from \$ 17,822.35 in 2016 to \$ 18,541.09 in 2017 in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal which indicates that the employees were more efficient in work

accomplishment in 2017. The factors behind the increase is due to the increase in manpower and also possibly because the technicians who started in 2016 have now gained more knowledge and thus are more efficient.

○ **Labor Productivity Per Employee at KTM Dagupan and Baguio**

The analysis of labor productivity per employee for KTM Dagupan and Baguio from August 2017 to April 2018 is as follows:

From August 2017 to April 2017, the total revenue generated was \$2,268.09 (Appendix H) and the total number of employees in the Service Department was four (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Labor Productivity Per Employee} &= (\$ 2,268.09)/4 \\ &= \$ 567.02 \end{aligned}$$

The labor productivity per employee in KTM Dagupan and Baguio is \$ 567.02. Since this outcome has no comparative variable internally, it can only be regarded as a margin for comparison after completion of operations in future.

Upon comparison between KTM in Nepal and Philippines, KTM in Nepal has a very high labor productivity per employee. Even while comparing the data from 2016, which is the first year of operation for KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal, the margin is significant. Higher labor productivity per employee in Nepal suggests that the manpower is being

efficiently utilized in order to achieve good revenues. Improvement in productivity in 2017 in Nepal suggests that market conditions are more suitable for KTM after-sales service business in Jawalakhel, Nepal than in Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines.

The high productivity ratio in Nepal could be because of the an already established market for KTM brand motorcycles in Nepal which is still in an early phase in the Philippines.

Labor productivity per day

Labor productivity per day denotes how efficiently the available working days have been utilized. Higher labor productivity per day signifies that available working hours have been effectively utilized by the workers.

o Labor productivity per day in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel

The analysis for labor productivity per day at KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal is as follows:

As informed by Mr. Umesh Dahal, in the year 2016, the total number of working days in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal was 272.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Labor Productivity Per Day} &= (\$ 320,802.28)/272 \\ &= \$ 1,179.42\end{aligned}$$

In 2017, the total number of working days in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal was 292.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Labor Productivity Per Day} &= (\$ 463,527.38)/292 \\ &= \$ 1,587.42\end{aligned}$$

The labor productivity per day in KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal increased from \$1,179.42 in 2016 to \$1,587.42 in 2017. One of the contributing factors behind the higher productivity is that in 2017 more working days were available which helped generate extra revenue. But the increase in productivity per day denotes that the available working time has been effectively utilized for improving revenue collections.

- **Labor productivity per day in KTM Dagupan and Baguio**

The analysis of labor productivity per day in KTM Dagupan and Baguio from August 2017 to April 2018 is as follows:

As informed by Mr. Dan Wigforss, from August 2017 to April 2017, the total number of working days was 224.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Labor Productivity Per Day} &= (\$ 2,268.09)/224 \\ &= \$ 10.25\end{aligned}$$

The labor productivity per day in KTM Dagupan and Baguio is \$10.25. Since this outcome has no comparative variable internally, it can only be regarded as a margin for comparison.

When the labor productivity per day between KTM Dagupan and Baguio and KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal are compared, it can be assessed that the margins in KTM Nepal have a significant yield. If KTM Nepal is taken as a benchmark for per day productivity, then it can be

established that KTM Dagupan and Baguio have to formulate effective strategies in order to boost market conditions as currently they are under-performing. But the data is also influenced by the market situation as the market and sales of KTM brand motorcycles are in an introductory phase in the Philippines. Due to this, the available working days have not produced a productive outcome in KTM Dagupan and Baguio.

Growth in labor productivity is directly attributable to fluctuations in physical capital, new technology and human capital. If labor productivity is growing, it can be traced back to growth in one of these three areas. It is also an important measure of the short-term and cyclical changes of the productive scenario in order to produce accurate strategies for optimum productivity.

Problems Encountered in the Motorcycle Servicing Business

Operations of KTM in Nepal and the Philippines

In every organization, problems are unavoidable. These problems could be major or minor which will both have an impact on the operations of the company. This segment of the study shall discuss the problems that have been identified during the study. These have been recognized through the report data assessment and through interview.

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal

In its business operation, KTM Service Center Jawalakhel

encounters the following problems which have been identified on the following sub-areas:

Organizational Aspects

The service center is highly dependent on manpower for accomplishment of the various service tasks. If the manpower does not perform efficiently then the jobs cannot be completed on time which directly affects the service volume and consequently the revenues as well. The major problem when it comes to this particular issue is the skill level of the new additions and the lack of skilled manpower for taking complex jobs.

The skilled manpower that are in the service center are in limited quantity. The service center received in an average 154 major jobs per month in 2017. The figure is higher than it was in 2016 (as per data from 2016, Appendix F) which was an average of 125 vehicles per month. But it's not a significant improvement and that is again due to lack of skilled manpower to take on the difficult tasks.

Furthermore, the skills levels are dependent on the level of trainings provided as well and for that the technicians need to be sent to India. But the problem here is that the only a few employees, usually two, are sent and that too after certain gaps. This raises the issue of uniformity in skills and negatively promotes lack of opportunity for self-development which is a demotivating factor. This demotivation can hamper pace of work which

might actually increase a normal service time by twice the intended time.

Service Process

KTM Service Center is a modern facility which was constructed in early 2016. The facility is intended to serve bigger volumes of vehicle and improve after sales service efficiency. But even though the layout has been well designed, certain expansions have become essential.

Set-up of more service ramps to accommodate more vehicle and help for performing faster servicing is now very essential. Moreover, since the ramps and equipment are getting older, timely maintenance is essential as well so that unscheduled need for maintenance does not affect the service operation. Also, the facility should try to digitalize the information systems and manage the job through real-time system so that the customer, the service advisor and the manager can keep track of the service progress easily. Also, spare parts unavailability and lack of stocks is a big issue.

The manager mentioned that the service center performed efficiently and almost to its full potential when the service centers operated under a temporary merger. This fact gives an impression that the service center is still underperforming even after addition on new employees in terms of service volume. Moreover, the service center volume is being affected by the time schedule which was till January 2018, from 9:30 am to 6 pm and since has been changed to 8 am to 9:30 pm. But the shift management and volume association as per the time allocation is yet another issue in

this regard.

Additionally, the lack of service ramps means that the service center takes in less volume than usual. And, the unmanaged task association as per the time further elevates the issues since the longer the time taken per service, lesser the volume of vehicles that can be accommodated per day.

Revenue Aspects

In case of revenue aspects, according to Mr. Umesh Dahal, the revenue generations have been higher than the previous year but in relation to this, the related costs of service, spare parts and lubricants have also increased. So, these do not exactly help associate the improvement. Furthermore, according to him, new manpower has been added and the maintenance charges are rising which might add pressure in financial target accomplishment in future.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines

KTM Dagupan and KTM Baguio are fairly new in terms of operating time so identification of problems is relatively difficult. But in its operations, KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines, encountered the following problems which have been identified in the following sub-areas:

Organizational Aspects

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio presently has some vacant positions which needs to be adhered to soon. The business will also have to think

about expansion plan and new positions assignment so that work functions can be divided, and employees can work with lesser distractions.

Service Process

Service category division is generalized which might create conflicts during work execution especially when multiple vehicles need simultaneous maintenance.

In case of workshop expansion, in order to comply with possible future rise in service volume, back-up expansion space must be allocated so that operations can remain smooth and efficient.

In case of service charge for various tasks, the business lacks a detailed allocation. This does not pose any significant problem, but the lack of detailed distinction does not easily enable to identify which tasks should be prioritized. Furthermore, the labor schedule does not indicate variations according to vehicle model which means labor price allocation for vehicles that take comparatively more time such as the RC range are not justified.

Revenue Aspects

The operation is relatively new so detailed assessment cannot be compiled but as informed by Mr. Dan Wigforss, shipment and availability of spare parts is the major concern. If this problem persists then it might affect the revenue generation severely.

Proposed Measures to Improve Motorcycle Servicing Business

Operation of KTM in Nepal and the Philippines

Every problem encountered is addressed with appropriate measure. The proposed measures have been established for both the countries after comparing the best practices available. These proposed measures will help the businesses to improve their operation and particularly in aspects related to organization, service process and revenue since these measures are practically based on the actual situation of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Service Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines, wherein an in-depth analysis and scrutiny has been commenced.

In addition, the proposed measures developed through the cross-learning will serve as a means of solving the various issues within the business operations even if it is in the smallest form. Furthermore, the measures will arise as a medium for change in the usual operations and practices in the businesses that have been under analysis due to issues related to overall operations improvement.

By implementing the proposed measures, KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio will be able to eliminate the problems and improve its service operations in future and will not encounter problem which have been faced in the past. This will thus help the businesses to become more efficient in terms of its operation

management.

Objectives

In this comparative study between operations of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, the researcher has the following objectives.

1. Extend assistance on how to improve the business operations through comparative learning
2. To propose preventive actions through comparison and best practices between the businesses in the two countries to avoid the reoccurrence of such problems that arise specifically in organization, service process and revenue aspects.
3. To recommend some ideas to improve the organization, service process and revenue aspects through cross-organization analysis and learnings.

To successfully attain the objectives, the various proposed measures have been enlisted for KTM Service, Jawalakhel and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio these are all in view of the problems encountered in the study.

These measures have been based on the best practices that have been derived from KTM Dagupan City and Baguio through the cross-learning. Also, proposed measures based on the researcher's observation which were not being practiced in either of the locations have also been

stated. These measures are as follows:

i. Proposed Measures for KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Nepal

a) Organization

Problems	Proposed Measures
No distinctive Training Category	<p>KTM Philippines has three different training categories: bronze, silver and gold. The levels ensure everyone gets training on basic to advanced level.</p> <p>This should also be implemented in KTM Nepal so that the technicians can develop on a similar pattern and can obtain similar set of skills. Furthermore, trainings on regular basis must be provided to all the employees. If sending to India on a regular basis is not a feasible option, then the local training facility must be improved so that the basic to intermediate level skills can be taught to the employees.</p>

b) Service Process

Problems	Proposed Measures
Lack of service ramps	At least three (3) more service ramps must be added in the facility in order to improve volume by decreasing the time taken per job.
Improving Spares Parts Availability	The spare parts must be stocked and stored in sufficient quantities so that the service operation is not hampered by the lack of spare parts or due to time spent on spare parts delivery.
Extending working hours	Working hours must be extended starting from early morning and shifts must be created with well-distributed manpower. The working days can also be changed from Sunday to Friday to Tuesday to Sunday and allocate Monday as a holiday so that the customers who remain busy during the weekdays can get their vehicle serviced.

c) Revenue

Problems	Proposed Measures
Increase in Maintenance Costs	Increase responsibility for every tool and equipment used so that everyone gives more attention during its application.

ii. Proposed Measures for KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines

a) Organization

Problems	Proposed Measures
Lack of job specific employee allocation for distinctive jobs	<p>KTM Service Centre Jawalakhel, Nepal has seven separate positions and each class has distinctive job specification. This division enables the employees to focus on a particular task and eliminates confusion and pressure through multiple job assignments. This also in turn has helped improve the operations in the service centre and the results are being seen in terms of service volume and revenues improvement.</p> <p>KTM Dagupan and Baguio only have three distinctions which means that each personnel has been assigned multiple job function. Job-specific employee allocation will help reduce the pressure on the employees and work productivity will improve.</p>

b) Service Process

Problems	Proposed Measures
No extensive Service Category Division	<p>KTM Service Centre Jawalakhel, Nepal has four service categories which helps manage the various maintenance and repair jobs and also helps allocate manpower effectively.</p> <p>KTM Dagupan and Baguio only have two categories. Additional of job categories might help in manpower allocation and time management as well.</p>
No Detailed division of labor schedule	<p>In KTM Service Centre Jawalakhel, Nepal labor scheduled has been divided in detail which for easier allocation of job and accurate assessment of the estimated labor charge.</p> <p>In KTM Dagupan and Baguio, the distinction is only in two categories, so amendments must be made so that the labor schedule can be more detailed and related price estimates can become more accurate.</p>

c) Revenue

Problems	Proposed Measures
Unavailability of Spare Parts	<p>Seek for alternative measures such as alternative shipping and spare parts purchase partners if the problem is persistent and no coordination is shown by the headquarter division.</p>

An assessment should also be undertaken upon implementing such measures to evaluate what are the areas that need special focus and attention. Also, a cross-country communication channel must be set-up so that both countries can share experience and learn from each other.

The competition in two-wheeler market segment in both Nepal and the Philippines is getting stiffer. One of the best ways to improve and sustain the market segment position is by providing exceptional after-sales service. KTM Service Center Jawalakhel and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, with the facility they have and by utilizing the above proposed measures, can strengthen their brand image and improve their market segment position.

Chapter V

SUMMARY CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This portion presents the summary of the findings, the conclusions arrived at and the recommendations offered.

Summary of the Findings

To determine accurately the operations of KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal, and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines, the findings presented in Chapter IV are hereby summarized.

Status of KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Lalitpur, Nepal and KTM Dagupan City and Baguio City, Philippines

Service Center operations of KTM in Nepal and the Philippines are maintained on a similar spectrum but slightly vary in terms of execution. The status of the operations has been studied with primary focus on three key aspects: Organizational Aspects, Service Process and Revenue Aspects. The findings herewith have been individually laid out and also compared so as to find areas of strength and improvement in both the locations.

Organizational Aspects

KTM Service Center Jawalakhel, Nepal has sufficient number of employees to look after the various operations but most of them are new and lack skill. This has partially affected the service operations but with

time and skill development, improvements are being seen gradually. Also, some employees lack motivation towards the job which is mainly due to lack of opportunities for development. But the skilled manpower who are present at the Service Center are working hard and giving their best efforts according to the manager. Additionally, the new helpers and even the technicians need to properly go through the SOP (Standard Operating Procedures) and the basic technical manuals so that they can stay on par with the improvements and can function efficiently.

KTM Dagupan City and Baguio, Philippines has a new facility and is relatively new in the two-wheeler market in Dagupan City and Baguio, so the business is still adapting. Management aspects such as job division would help the business as it grows. Constant learning and developmental opportunities should be provided alongside the KTM Service training that is provided.

In terms of productivity ratio, KTM in both countries is performing well. The management of productivity above the generally stated baseline suggests that KTM management pays special attention while formulating management plan globally.

Service Process

The KTM Service Center, Jawalakhel in Nepal can be easily located as it is situated in the town center. The layout is well designed and has properly utilized the area allocated. The drawbacks seem to be the parking

area which at present serves both as parking space for the vehicles coming to the service center and also as the arrangement space for delivery ready vehicles. The insufficient space creates problems specially during peak hours. Allocation of parking and delivery ready vehicle distribution space need special attention if the service center wants to expand its service volume. Another problem that has been a highlighted issue in the current days is the lack of service ramps which is directly affecting the service time and hence the service volume. The facility has sufficient space wherein four (4) extra ramps can be added and this needs to be a priority if the service volume is to be increased.

Additionally, according to Mr. Umesh Dahal, the service volume management is the key target of the service center as everything is dependent on managing the flow of vehicles in the service center. The service volume has been on a rise compared to the previous year but still has not reached the peak that it should. But the issue is under execution phase through the expansion of employee pool and possible dual working shift implementation.

KTM Dagupan City and KTM Baguio, Philippines are located in popular and accessible areas in respective cities. The layout plan of Dagupan City is well designed and has incorporated all the important aspects of a layout design such as safety plans and space management. The drawbacks seem to be in the service type distinction and generalized

the labor charge schedule. But as the operations are settling, the business is slowing evolving and might look into more options in future. But at present, operations are still under a planning phase and it might not seem necessary to bring these changes right away.

KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal has a significantly high Repair Order per technician which is 186.5 which in KTM Dagupan and Baguio it is 12.75. Lower number signify stress-free work environment but also signify that opportunities for growth and business expansion is restricted.

Revenue

After special request made by Mr. Umesh Dahal to the financial department, only the revenue of the service charge, spare parts sales and lubricants sale were available. Though the financial aspects illustrated by the revenue seem positive, but the lack of extended financial reports means that a clear financial stance cannot be assessed. Furthermore, on a side note, according to the manager, the facility maintenance cost is increasing and the plan for installing new service ramps might add financial pressure to the overall management as well.

In the case of KTM Dagupan and Baguio, since they are still in their early days of operation, making a detailed assessment was not possible. But as the operation grows, it will become easier to identify further areas of improvement. But on current evaluation, the area that's affecting the revenue generation is the lack of availability of spare parts. As spares parts

is the core earning area of any vehicle service business, lack of parts directly affects the overall revenue.

KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal is more productive in terms on productivity per employee per day. Higher productivity suggests increased revenue and prosperous business. KTM Dagupan and Baguio, Philippines are in their early year of operation so have a lower productivity. But constant market assessment and strategies formulation is necessary in order to magnify growth and improve revenue.

Problems in KTM Service Jawalakhel in Nepal can be closely associated with the lack of forecasting in terms of infrastructure, personnel development and lack of optimization in process flow. In KTM Dagupan and Baguio in the Philippines, since it is a new establishment, the concerns are on distinctive positions and roles and on need for faster process flow on handling specific spare parts requirement.

Both the countries can learn from each other's practices for better operational control. Nepal can learn from the Philippines in terms of training schedules while the Philippines can learn from Nepal in terms of aspects required to expand the after-sales servicing business and improve productivity. The identified measures in turn can help KTM to gain a better understanding of various markets and formulate strategic plans to grow in new environment with accordance to the variances present.

Conclusion

Based on the findings in this study, the subsequent conclusions were drawn.

Foremost, it can be concluded that there are a lot of similarities between the service departments in both the countries. Most of the policies and work ethics of KTM can be seen being implemented on a similar spectrum regardless of variations in culture, market situation and operational protocols. One key conclusion is that KTM has maintained a global standard even when there is a contrasting market situation.

Another deduction from the study is that there are areas which have not been utilized to their potential. Special focus must be given to facility management, employee training and function division. Additionally, continuous learning opportunities should be provided to maintain efficiency and improve the operations.

Additionally, it can also be inferred from the study that after-sales market gain in a new location is a gradual process which requires patience and dedication. The level of acceptance and understanding from the consumer market affects the perception of the quality of service and thus it is highly essential to train the employees and provide them with sufficient exposure to handle clients effectively.

The proposed measures will aim to formulate strategies and actions

to deal with the issues and concerns on the aspect of organization, service process and revenue which will eventually help enhance their operations and should provide improvement measures for both countries.

Recommendations

The future of KTM Service operations will depend on how they will adapt to the increasing modern trends in service industry. Most automobile service centers in developed countries have real-time online data systems which helps in pre-assessment of and prediction of customer flow over a period. This especially helps to manage the volume of vehicles and hence achieve higher volume and generate greater revenues. KTM in both countries have modern systems implemented and are close in terms of directives, but they still need to learn and grow from systems which are almost obsolete in most of the developed countries.

In consideration of the foregoing conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

1. The KTM Service Centers in Nepal and the Philippines may consider employee training and work-division reassessment for better productivity and service quality.
2. In order to have an objective basis in strengthening the service center operations of KTM Service Jawalakhel, Nepal and KTM Dagupan and Baguio, parallel and further studies are encouraged.

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LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY

March 9, 2018

Mr. Umesh Dahal,
Service Center Manager
KTM Service Center Jawalakhel
Lalitpur, Nepal

Respected Sir,

In line with the partial requirement of Master in Business Administration, I am conducting a study entitled, “Comparative Study of the Operations of Motorcycle Service Centers in Nepal and Philippines”. The purpose of this study is to analyze the service operations of the KTM Service business in both the countries and for the successful completion of this study, your contributions will help to provide meaningful information and also help increase our understanding in bringing about growth and development in the Automobile Service Industry.

Hence, with this, I am requesting your permission to allow me to interview you and provide the data of the service volume, service charges, and any other related document, if be necessary.

I assure you that the information will remain confidential and will be used for the research purposes only.

Thank you for your time and effort and hoping for your positive response.

With Best Regards,
(SGD) Mr. Sandesh Giri

LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY

April 18, 2018

Mr. Dan Wigforss,
Chief Operations Officer
Ecg Zoom Zone Inc,
Dagupan City, Pangasinan

Respected Sir,

In line with the partial requirement of Master in Business Administration, I am conducting a study entitled, “Comparative Study of the Operations of Motorcycle Service Centers in Nepal and Philippines”. The purpose of this study is to analyze the service operations of the KTM Service business in both the countries and for the successful completion of this study, your contributions will help to provide meaningful information and also help increase our understanding in bringing about growth and development in the Automobile Service Industry.

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Thank you for your time and effort and hoping for your positive response.

With Best Regards,
(SGD) Mr. Sandesh Giri

INTERVIEW GUIDE

A. Company background

1. When and how was the service center established?
2. What is the nature of business at KTM Service Center/Department?
3. Please describe the classification of vehicles that are serviced in the facility.

B. The status of service operation of KTM Service Center in terms of:

1. Organization

- a. How many employees are there in the service center?
- b. What is the organizational structure?
- c. What are their duties and responsibilities?
- d. How are they selected and trained?

2. Service Process

- a. What is the operational procedure?
- b. Please explain the facility layout?
- c. What modern information management software are used?
- d. What is the service flow process?

- e. What are the various levels of service jobs?
- f. What tools and equipment are available in the service center?
- g. Please explain the service volume status at the service center in the recent years?
- h. What factors are involved in service volume management?
- i. What are the various service job timings?
- j. What are the factors that influence variable job timings?
- k. May I have a copy of the service volume record for the year 2016 and 2017?

3. Revenue (Service, Spares and Lubricants Revenue)

- a. What is the state of revenue generation in terms of service charge, spare parts sales and lubricants sale in the last two years?
- b. What are factors that have influenced the rise or fall in the revenue generation?
- c. May I have a copy of the revenue for the FY 2016-2017 and FY 2017-2018/ 2017-2018?

C. Problems encountered and proposed measures

- 1. What are the problems faced or issues on the following and how did you handle them?

- a. Organization
 - b. Service Process
 - c. Revenue
2. Are there any other issues that you would like to share?

COMPANY LOGO

Figure 11: Logo of KTM

Figure 12: Logo of Hansraj Hulaschand & Co.Pvt.Ltd, the sole official distributor of KTM Motorcycles in Nepal

Figure 13: Logo of ecg Zoom Zone Inc, the authorized Authorised KTM Dealer in Baguio, Dagupan Pangasinan & San Fernando La Union

Appendix E

Revenue Generated in KTM Service, Jawalakhel in FY 2016-2017

	FY 2016-2017
Service Charge	\$ 25,206.77
Spares Sales	\$ 217,440.16
Lubricants Sales	\$ 78,161.34
Total	\$ 320,808.28

Appendix F

Service Volume in KTM Service Center Jawalakhel in 2016

	2016				
	Periodic Free Service	Periodic Paid Service	Major Repairs	QRC	Monthly Total
January	-	-	-	-	-
February	48	39	92	150	329
March	81	98	59	187	425
April	60	92	44	200	396
May	84	115	63	279	541
June	93	125	66	235	519
July	117	165	97	287	666
August	181	150	240	468	1039
September	186	171	226	471	1054
October	180	119	188	354	841
November	215	128	198	512	1053
December	152	147	111	377	787
Total	1397	1349	1384	3520	7650

Appendix G

**Service Volume at KTM Dagupan and Baguio from January to April
2018**

	2018			
	Periodic Paid Service	Major Repairs	QRC	Total
January	18	1	6	26
February	18	1	3	22
March	10	2	2	16
April	7	-	1	8
	53	4	12	72

Appendix H

**Revenue Generated at KTM Dagupan and Baguio from August 2017
to April 2018**

	2017 (Aug-Dec)	2018 (Jan-Apr)	2017-2018
Service Charge	\$ 86.59	\$ 99.88	\$ 186.48
Spares Sales	\$ 430.10	\$ 543.60	\$ 973.70
Lubricants Sales	\$ 438.69	\$ 669.23	\$ 1,107.91
Total	\$ 955.38	\$ 1,312.72	\$ 2,268.09